

**AZERBAIJAN
STANDARDIZATION
INSTITUTE**

«STANDARDS FOR SUSTAINABLE GREEN FUTURE»

**II INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC-PRACTICAL SYMPOSIUM
DEDICATED TO THE “GREEN WORLD SOLIDARITY YEAR”
AND “WORLD STANDARDS DAY”**

14 October 2024

ASOIU, Department of Instrumentation Engineering

ABSTRACTS PROCEEDINGS

Associate Professor, Acting Rector ASOIU Vazeh Asgarov

From 1995 to 1999, he obtained a bachelor's degree in French and English languages at Azerbaijan University of Languages. In 2003, he was admitted to the University of Robert Schuman in France. In 2003-2004, he pursued a Certificate in International and European Law, and in 2004, he was admitted to the University of Robert Schuman in France. From 2004 to 2006, he continued his studies for a Master's degree in Linguistics at Marc Bloch University in Strasbourg. From 2007 to 2012, he pursued doctoral studies on "The migration of Azerbaijanis to France: history and perspectives" at the Department of European Society and Culture at the University of Strasbourg and in 2012, he was awarded a Doctorate from the University of Strasbourg.

The doctoral diploma from the University of Strasbourg was nostrified by the State Examination Commission under the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan in February 2016 and was recorded in history as the first French doctoral diploma to be re-attested in Azerbaijan. On February 18, 2019, based on the decision of the State Attestation Commission under the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Vazeh Askarov was awarded a diploma of Doctor of Philosophy and Associate Professor in history.

Ilham Bayramov graduated in 1992 from the Faculty of Soil Science and Agrochemistry of Moscow State University, named after M.V. Lomonosov. In 2002, he completed the "Strategic Research and State Defense Management Academic Courses" at the Military Academy of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Azerbaijan. From 2006 to 2009, he graduated with honors from the Faculty of "Advanced Training of Executive Personnel" at the Academy of Public Administration under the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan.

Xamis Seyranov. He was born on October 2, 1984, in the Salyan district. From 2001 to 2007, he studied Law at Baku State University, where he completed his bachelor's degree and later pursued a master's degree. He served in the military from 2007 to 2008. From 2010 to 2013, he pursued postgraduate studies in Civil Law at the Institute of Philosophy, Sociology, and Law of the Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences. In 2016, he earned a Ph.D. in Law. By the order of the Ministry of Economy of Azerbaijan dated July 22, 2024, he was appointed as the Director-General of the "Azerbaijan Metrology Institute" public legal entity.

Arzu Gulhan Yuzereroglu, Turkish Standards Institute
Azerbaijan Representative, ISO 9001,14001,45001 50001
Lead Auditor

Darkhan Yerezhep, PhD, Head of the Department of Standardization, Certification and Metrology

2015-2017 - Master's degree - ITMO National Research University; 2017-2020 - Postgraduate studies - ITMO National Research University, Faculty of Training of Highly qualified Personnel, direction: "Physics and Astronomy". April 2021 - Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) majoring in Technical Physics. 09.2015-05.2016 – Assistant of the Department of Energy Materials, Faculty of Low-Temperature Power Engineering, National Research University ITMO, 04.2023-09.2023 – Leading Researcher, Institute of Physics and Technology, Almaty, 09.2023-present-Ass.Professor, Department of Standardization, Certification and Metrology, Institute of Power Engineering and Mechanical Engineering, KazNITU named after K.I. Satpayev.

Prof. Lala Rustam Bakirova, Doctor of Technical science, head of department "Instrumentation Engineering", ASOIU, Azerbaijan Bakirova Lala Rustam received the M.Sc. and Ph.D. degrees from Azerbaijan institute of Oil and Chemistry in 1985 and 1998, respectively. She received the Doctor of Technical Sciences in 2016. Professor and Head of Department Instrumentation Engineering Azerbaijan State Oil and Industrial University. Azerbaijan EAC under the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, expert on technical sciences. Founder member of the International Scientific Association of Scientists ALIM. She is head of department "Instrumentation Engineering", Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University.

II International Scientific-Practical Symposium on "Standards for Sustainable Green Future" held at ASOIU On October 14, the II International Scientific-Practical Symposium titled "Standards for Sustainable Green Future," dedicated to the "Green World Solidarity Year" and "World Standards Day" started at Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University (ASOIU).

The symposium, organized by the Department of Instrumentation Engineering, took place in a hybrid format, both online and offline. The opening ceremony began with the playing of the National Anthem of Azerbaijan, followed by a minute of silence in honor of National Leader Heydar Aliyev and the martyrs who gave their lives for the territorial integrity of Azerbaijan.

In his opening remarks at the symposium, ASOIU's Acting Rector, Associate Professor Vazeh Asgarov, welcomed the participants and highlighted the significance of President Ilham Aliyev's declaration of 2024 as the "Green World Solidarity Year" in the context of global climate change and the shift towards green energy. He also emphasized the importance of hosting this international scientific symposium at the university, especially ahead of a major event like COP29.

Associate Professor Asgarov also spoke about ASOIU's recent achievements in global university rankings and stressed the vital role of educating young people about sustainable green futures and the implementation of new standards. He reaffirmed the university's support for all initiatives in this area.

Ilham Bayramov, Director General of the Azerbaijan Institute of Standardization, and Khamis Seyranov, Director General of the Azerbaijan Institute of Metrology, discussed the country's efforts related to climate change, the implementation of new standards, and the role of youth in adopting green technologies. They praised the symposium's work and its contribution to these important topics.

Gülhan Arzu Yüzereroğlu, head of the Turkish Standards Institute (TSE) representative office in Azerbaijan, and Darkhan Erezhap, Dean of Satbayev University in Kazakhstan, joined the symposium online, noting the scientific significance of the event and its alignment with modern global challenges.

Finally, Professor Lala Bakirova, head of the Department of Instrumentation Engineering, provided detailed information about the symposium. She emphasized its role in the exchange of experiences, the study and application of alternative energy resources, and the development of scientific potential and mutual collaboration.

Prof. Lala Bakirova
ASOİU, ITCF,
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Ph.D. Kamala Mammadzade
AZSTAND, Deputy General
Director – Director of
Department of Standardization

Ass. Prof. Maya Karimova
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TOPICS OF THE SYMPOSIUM

- **BUILDING A GREEN WORLD: RENEWABLE ENERGY FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT**
- **QUALITY CONTROL AND MONITORING SYSTEMS;**
- **HIGH PRECISION ENGINEERING STANDARDS;**
- **INTELLIGENT MEASUREMENT AND CONTROL TECHNOLOGIES FOR A GREEN FUTURE;**
- **INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS IN PROJECT MANAGEMENT;**
- **SMART BIOMEDICAL TECHNOLOGIES FOR A SUSTAINABLE GREEN FUTURE;**
- **ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE FOR A SUSTAINABLE GREEN FUTURE;**
- **INFORMATION SECURITY STANDARDS FOR THE STATE, SOCIETY AND INDIVIDUALS;**

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE FOR A SUSTAINABLE GREEN FUTURE

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ABSTRACT

Green Sustainable Future with the Help of Artificial Intelligence. Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a transformational tool that can change how sustainability is approached in a wide array of sectors. This paper explores the multi-dimensional uses of artificial intelligence in solving some of the most pressing environmental challenges and ensuring a sustainable future, including resource management, climate change mitigation, and agriculture. The use of AI may optimize resource consumption by analyzing historical data, predicting trends, and identifying inefficiencies in real-time. Climate change mitigation efforts can benefit from AI-driven models that can predict such patterns and maybe even pinpoint the weakest regions, informing policy decisions and contributing to innovative solutions in carbon capture technologies. AI might boost productivity and sustainability in agriculture by optimizing irrigation methods, and fertilizer application within an extensive analysis of data. However, challenges do arise when deploying AI in sustainability efforts. Key ethical considerations include data privacy, algorithmic bias, and employment displacement. Strong ethical frameworks and responsible AI practices are required for the minimization of risks and maximization of benefits from the development of AI. The capabilities of AI can be harnessed responsibly across a range of sectors for the purpose of making the planet more sustainable and resilient, transforming our approach to environmental stewardship and resource management.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Ethical AI, Sustainability, Climate Change.

Calibration as a Method for Uncertainty Reduction in Green Standards

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the crucial role of calibration in reducing measurement uncertainty, particularly in green standards designed to promote sustainability and minimize environmental impact. Green standards, such as ISO 14001 for environmental management and LEED for sustainable construction, rely on precise data to verify compliance with goals related to energy efficiency, emissions reduction, and resource

conservation. Calibration ensures that measurement Instrumentations used in environmental monitoring are accurate, reliable, and traceable to national or international standards, significantly reducing uncertainty in data collection.

Measurement uncertainty can lead to incorrect reporting, undermining the credibility of sustainability claims and resulting in non-compliance with environmental regulations. By integrating calibration into the processes of green standard compliance, organizations can not only improve the accuracy of environmental performance data and enhance operational efficiency and regulatory adherence. This article outlines practical strategies for implementing effective calibration practices, including developing robust calibration plans, partnering with accredited providers, and maintaining comprehensive documentation.

Furthermore, the article highlights how regular calibration of Instrumentations used in renewable energy systems, emissions monitoring, and waste management directly contributes to better decision-making and enhances an organization's sustainability credentials. As green technologies evolve and stricter regulations emerge, reducing uncertainty through calibration becomes increasingly vital for achieving sustainable development goals. In conclusion, calibration is a key prerequisite for precise and reliable data in environmental initiatives, playing a crucial role in the success of green standards and promoting a more sustainable future.

Keywords: Calibration, Measurement uncertainty, Green Standards, Sustainability, Environmental Compatibility, ISO 14001, Metrology traceable

METROLOGICAL SUPPORT IN STANDARDIZATION

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ABSTRACT

The article examines the importance of metrological support in the context of standardization as a key element that promotes the unity and reliability of measurements in various industries and sciences. It analyzes the main aspects of metrological support, including the development and implementation of standards, calibration and verification procedures, and training of specialists. Metrological support in standardization plays a key role in ensuring the uniformity and accuracy of measurements, which is a prerequisite for maintaining the quality of products and services in all sectors of the economy. In today's world, where competition is becoming increasingly tough, organizations must ensure that their products meet certain standards, which is only possible with a reliable metrological system.

One aspect of metrological support is the training of specialists involved in measurements and their interpretation. Qualified personnel are necessary for the correct implementation of metrological procedures and ensuring compliance with legislative and industry requirements.

The implementation of metrological support in standardization helps to increase the competitiveness of products, reduce production risks and increase consumer confidence. It also allows organizations to optimize their processes, reducing measurement errors and increasing efficiency.

In Table 1 I show metrological support in standardization.

Table 1.

Aspect	Description
Target	Ensuring the uniformity and accuracy of measurements to support the quality of products and services.
Standards	Development and implementation of national and international standards for the comparability of measurements.
Calibration and verification	Regular procedures to check the accuracy of measuring instrumentations in accordance with established standards.
Training of specialists	Training of personnel involved in metrological measurements and their interpretation.
Documentation	Maintaining records and documentation related to metrological support and measurement results.

Thus, metrological support in standardization is an integral part of the successful functioning of modern business, contributing not only to improving the quality of products, but also to the creation of a sustainable system of interaction between producers and consumers at the global level.

Keywords: metrological, standardization, standard, measurement, accuracy, industry

STANDARDS FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

International standards play a significant and strategic role in ensuring sustainable development. These standards aim at more efficient resource management, environmental protection, and the formation of sustainable systems for the future of humanity. The principles and approaches validated through standards lead to significant changes, especially in areas such as ensuring energy efficiency, reducing carbon emissions, smart resource utilization, and more effective waste management. Measures adopted and implemented in line with COP29 objectives, particularly regarding energy

efficiency and carbon emissions reduction, strengthen Azerbaijan's green transformation and serve as a fundamental step on this path. International standards offer environmentally safer and more sustainable approaches for both industrial and other sectors.

Incorporating standards into production processes results in optimized and more efficient production systems, reduced energy consumption, and better waste management. This approach provides enterprises with economic and competitive advantages while enabling them to fulfill their environmental responsibilities. Efficient use of energy resources not only enhances competitiveness in the production sector but also raises economic efficiency through lower raw material consumption and increased potential for reuse. For example, the implementation of the ISO 14001 standard reduces negative environmental impacts, while ISO 50001 optimizes energy use, improving enterprise performance and overall production capacity. This prevents energy wastage and allows enterprises to use resources smartly.

Future Perspectives and Challenges:

Additional measures are being implemented to overcome obstacles in the process of applying standards and to promote the broader development of green technologies. These measures also involve the application of more modern and effective mechanisms that enhance economic competitiveness, ensure nature conservation, and minimize environmental impacts. In the future, the wider application of standards is expected to yield even greater positive results in terms of environmental efficiency. These trends could pave the way for significant changes to achieve sustainable development goals, providing broader environmental, social, and economic benefits.

These points highlight the importance of integrating international standards and green technologies to achieve sustainable development goals.

Keywords: sustainable development, energy efficiency, carbon emissions, green technology, resource optimization, ISO 14001, ISO 50001, COP29.

OPENING THE DOOR TO A GREEN FUTURE: MINIMIZING ECOLOGICAL IMPACT IN NATURAL GAS STORAGE

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ABSTRACT

Natural gas plays a crucial role in modern energy production; however, its storage processes lead to significant ecological concerns. Carbon emissions, methane leaks, and

other pollutants generated during natural gas storage not only harm the atmosphere but also threaten groundwater resources, air quality, and the health of ecosystems. Therefore, the implementation of intelligent control systems is essential to reduce ecological impacts.

Intelligent control systems are advanced technologies equipped with capabilities for data collection, analysis, and real-time forecasting. These systems assist in optimizing energy production processes, enhancing resource efficiency, and detecting potential leaks in a timely manner. For example, they monitor weather changes and natural gas demand, thereby improving production efficiency. As a result, this approach significantly reduces carbon emissions. Research shows that when intelligent control systems are applied, energy production efficiency increases, and ecological impacts are minimized.

The integration of new technologies is also vital in modern energy production. Artificial intelligence, big data analysis, and automation systems can make energy production more effective and ecologically sustainable. Such innovations lead to lower carbon emissions during natural gas storage while ensuring that energy production is more reliable. Intelligent systems help enterprises detect leaks and other environmental issues promptly, allowing operators to minimize risks and adopt more responsible practices.

Ultimately, this research emphasizes the importance of applying intelligent control systems in natural gas storage for increasing energy production efficiency and reducing ecological impacts. The development of modern approaches for sustainable growth not only cleans up energy production but also plays a significant role in protecting ecosystems.

These approaches ensure that the needs of future generations are met while facilitating the creation of a more sustainable and environmentally friendly energy system. Thus, the application of intelligent control systems plays an invaluable role in balancing ecological protection and energy efficiency.

Keywords: natural gas, energy production, ecological impacts, carbon emissions, intelligent control systems, efficiency, new technologies, sustainable development.

INTELLIGENT LOAD SHARING IN DIFFERENT CAPABLE POWER GENERATION SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Load sharing is a critical concept for power generation, where multiple generators or power sources are used to supply number of demands with different power rating. The increasing complexity of power grids, with a mix of conventional and renewable energy sources, requires efficient load-sharing mechanisms or algorithm to ensure stability, reliability, and optimal power generation performance.

This article discusses load sharing in different types of power generation systems, focusing on both conventional power plants and distributed renewable energy systems.

Smart grid technologies, energy storage, and hybrid power systems are key to overcoming the challenges associated with load sharing in different capable power generation systems. In today's interconnected world, reliable and efficient power distribution is a critical component of modern infrastructure.

Electrical load sharing plays a significant role in maintaining system stability, ensuring that power is distributed with normal manner. Electrical load sharing refers to the distribution of electrical power across multiple generators or power sources to balance the load demand.

This concept is especially relevant in scenarios where multiple power generation units, such as diesel generators, gas turbines, or renewable energy sources, work together in parallel to meet the electricity demands of a given system with various loads without overloading any part of the grid power generation system. This article explores the principles, benefits, and challenges of electrical load sharing, highlighting its importance in optimizing energy usage and promoting sustainability. Key principles of load sharing are the total electrical demand is divided among available generators based on their capacity and operational status. This helps prevent overloads and ensures a stable power supply. Load sharing involves managing both real (active) power and reactive power.

Keywords: load sharing, power generation, demand, smart grid, power system stability, real power.

REMOTE CONTROL OF THE SURFACE TEMPERATURE OF OBJECTS, TAKING INTO ACCOUNT EXTERNAL FACTORS

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ABSTRACT

The article considers methods of remote control of the surface temperature of objects, taking into account external factors - both internal and external factors, and the influence of external factors when remotely controlling the surface temperature of objects. To remotely control the surface temperature, 3 platforms of remote control - ground platforms (cranes, towers, etc.), air platforms (helicopters, airplanes, unmanned aerial vehicles, and drones), and space platforms (spaceships, geostationary satellites, polar-orbiting satellites) and modern sensors controlling these platforms were used. An overview was presented, many types were considered, their classification, application areas, and characteristics were described, advantages and disadvantages were analyzed, and factors controlling surface temperature such as altitude, latitude, relief, air mass circulation ocean currents, and wind were considered.

Among the remote control sensors, remote temperature and thermal infrared sensors were used as the most appropriate sensors, and surface temperature readings were

obtained with their help. A complex block diagram and algorithmic model were proposed to measure the surface temperature of objects and control the temperature.

The application areas and operating principles of remote temperature sensors were considered, compared with other temperature sensors, their advantages and disadvantages compared to other sensors were analyzed, and the issues that form the basis of their work were considered.

These proposed sensors can work with remote surfaces in a wide range and allow measuring high temperatures from long distances, reading information quickly before the measurements begin, obtaining more accurate information, and providing accurate information, increasing the accuracy of measuring surface temperature with remote temperature sensors without contact with the controlled object and from a long distance, and controlling the surface temperature of the object quickly and with high accuracy.

Keywords: object, surface temperature of objects, remote control, external factors, remote temperature sensors, contact temperature sensors, contactless temperature sensors, infrared sensors.

ALIGNING STANDARDS WITH THE GLOBAL GREEN AGENDA: INTEGRATING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE FOR SUSTAINABLE SOLUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

The global shift towards sustainability has brought about the increase in international standards and the Green Agenda's convergence. The countries, in their goal of very ambitious environmental objectives, are obliged to include high technologies like Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the construction of long-term solutions. This thesis is concerned with the connection between AI and international standards, highlighting how AI can be employed for improvement of the environmental sustainability in various fields. It deals with the role of AI in the improvement of the use of resources and the consequent reduction of emissions, as well as the endorsement of cleaner production methods, mentioning its effect to environmental monitoring and conformity to green standards at the exact time.

The capability of AI to process vast amounts of information in real-time has a potential to create new solutions that will automate and improve green initiatives, for instance, smart grids, measuring carbon footprint, and developing energy-efficient systems.

Through associating AI-based means with the existing environmental norms, the industries can boost the performance of the devices while at the same time, they remain on the right side of the green transition pathway. The study also indicates potential impediments and ethical contradictions that can emerge from the use of AI, particularly in ensuring transparency, accountability, and equity in the decision-making process.

In addition, the research investigates the rise of international standard-setting bodies to supervise AI for sustainability and ensure that AI solutions comply with global climate change objectives. This study is aimed at indicating a clear strategy for the policymakers, businessmen, and scientists to exploit AI as the main tool in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) but carrying forward the global environmental demands.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Sustainability, Green Agenda, Environmental Standards, Sustainable Development Goals, Resource Efficiency, Compliance.

ATOMIC CLOCKS AND SUSTAINABILITY: THE ROLE OF METROLOGICAL ASSURANCE IN MODERN GREEN TECHNOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT

Atomic clocks are critical to modern technological systems, ensuring the precision and reliability necessary for applications like global navigation satellite systems (GNSS), telecommunications, scientific research, and financial operations. With the global push toward sustainability, the role of atomic clocks in enabling green technologies is increasingly vital. This research paper examines the essential metrological assurance processes associated with atomic clocks and their contributions to sustainable technological advancements.

Metrological assurance, which includes calibration, traceability to international time standards (UTC), and uncertainty management, is fundamental in maintaining the accuracy of atomic clocks. These timekeeping systems support key infrastructures such as smart energy grids, optimized transportation networks, and satellite-based environmental monitoring systems.

Accurate synchronization provided by atomic clocks is essential for improving energy efficiency, reducing waste, and ensuring the reliability of systems that monitor climate and environmental changes. This paper discusses how precise timekeeping enables greener processes, making atomic clocks integral to achieving environmental sustainability.

Additionally, the development of low-power, highly durable atomic clocks is explored, highlighting their potential to minimize environmental impact while maintaining the necessary precision. The advancements in atomic clock technology align with green standards by reducing energy consumption and increasing the longevity of these devices, which is crucial for long-term sustainability.

The paper also addresses the challenges of balancing the growing demand for ultra-precise timekeeping with the need to reduce the environmental footprint of these systems.

By integrating atomic clock technology into sustainable technological ecosystems, this paper demonstrates how precision timekeeping can drive innovations in energy management, resource optimization, and environmental protection.

The discussion emphasizes the importance of international standards, collaboration, and innovation in ensuring the long-term sustainability of atomic clocks in modern green technologies. Ultimately, this research underscores the critical role that atomic clocks play in facilitating the transition to a sustainable future, where metrological assurance supports both technological progress and environmental stewardship.

Keywords: atomic clocks, precision timekeeping, metrological assurance, sustainable technologies, energy efficiency, environmental monitoring, international standards (UTC).

REFLECTING SUNLIGHT AFTER DARK VIA REFLECTOR ORBITAL MIRRORS

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ABSTRACT

In the realm of renewable energy innovation, the concept of harnessing sunlight after dark through the use of reflector orbital mirrors has emerged as a compelling frontier. The deployment of orbital mirrors in outer space to reflect sunlight onto specific locations on Earth during nighttime hours presents a unique opportunity for continuous solar power utilization. This visionary approach not only promises the potential for around-the-clock energy generation but also raises significant technological, economic, and environmental considerations. This abstract delves into the theoretical framework and implications of utilizing orbital mirrors to reflect sunlight after dark, highlighting the challenges and opportunities associated with this ambitious endeavor. Reflecting sunlight after dark using orbital mirrors is a concept that has been proposed in the realm of space-based solar power. The idea involves placing large mirrors in space that can reflect sunlight onto specific locations on Earth even during nighttime hours. This technology could potentially harness solar power continuously, providing a potential solution for around-the-clock energy generation. However, there are significant technical, economic, and environmental challenges associated with implementing such a system. Theoretically, by adjusting the angle of these mirrors in orbit, it would be possible to focus the reflected sunlight onto selected areas, even during nighttime hours, effectively creating a form of artificial daylight. While this idea presents intriguing possibilities, it is important to note that the practical implementation of such a system would involve numerous challenges, including the precision required to target specific locations, the cost of deploying and maintaining orbital mirrors, as well as potential concerns related to light pollution and environmental impacts. REFERENCES 1) Mirrors and Reflections/ Alexandre V. Borovik;

by Alexandre V. Borovik, Anna Borovik. By: Borovik, Alexandre V. 2) Mirror-3DGS: Incorporating Mirror Reflections into 3D Gaussian Splatting/ Meng, Jiarui; Li, Haijie; Wu, Yanmin; Gao, Qiankun; Yang, Shuzhou; Zhang, Jian; Ma, Siwei 2024 3) A Search for Peculiar Objects with the NASA Orbital Debris Observatory 3-m Liquid Mirror Telescope Published in: 19980424 Database: arXiv / Cabanac, R.; Borra, E.F.; Beauchemin, M.

Keywords: Orbital Mirrors; Sunlight; Night Illumination; Space Technology; Reflection; Commercial Lightning.

COMPARISON OF SIMULATED EV'S ENERGY CONSUMPTION WITH PHYSICAL ROAD TEST

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, due to the limited fuel resources for the increasing energy demand, the search for alternative energy sources in transportation and in many different sectors continues rapidly. In this study, mathematical modeling of an electric minibus used in urban transportation in daily life was made in MATLAB/Simulink environment. The technical and dynamic features of the vehicle were used in the modeling. According to the UITP Project E-Sort procedure, Standardized On-Road Test Cycles-1 (Sort-1), Sort-2 and Sort-3 road conditions were applied to the vehicle modeled in the simulation environment. Energy consumption and maximum distance rates that the vehicle can travel with a full charge were calculated in 3 different road conditions. As a result of the study, thanks to the data obtained from the simulation environment it is aimed to obtain an approximate maximum range data that the vehicle can get while it is in the design phase before the physical test, with less cost. Studies on mathematical modeling and development of electrical vehicles (EVs), the use of which are rapidly becoming widespread, have been increasing. Component changes made according to physical test results in prototype vehicles cause losses in terms of time and cost. With this study, it is aimed to compare the simulation results with the physical test results. Then, with the data obtained from the comparison results, it is aimed to perform the maximum distance and energy consumption test in the simulation environment before the prototype vehicle is produced, thus minimizing the loss of time and cost. In this study, a mathematical model of an electric minibus used in urban transportation was created according to its dynamic characteristics and energy consumption was calculated in simulation. MATLAB Simulink is used in the scope of this study. Additional to simulation study and mathematical modelling, physical tests are also performed to compare simulated results. According to the UITP PROJECT E-SORT procedure, the prototype vehicle was instrumented with the data logger, GPS, V-

Box devices connected to the Can communication path of the vehicle and the energy consumption amount is observed. Within the scope of this study, it is aimed to compare the simulation results with the data obtained as a result of the test. As a result of the study, the accuracy of the results obtained in the simulation with physical tests, the margin of error and the deviations in maximum distance calculations evaluated.

Keywords Electric Vehicle, Energy Consumption Calculation, Mathematical modeling, Physical Energy Consumption.

WRIST REHABILITATION MEDICAL DEVICE

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ABSTRACT

The projection of the control system consists in the development of an intuitively controllable mechanism that aims to accept the parameters defined by the user and respond through the request. In order to achieve the interface between the user and the mechanism, two methods are used, one of which is oriented to electronic hardware and another to data acquisition software. In the first one is given the commands and instructions and in the second one is collected and registered all the information. Since such mechanisms already exist, it is intended that this case of study and development of the product will cover the inconveniences left by such equipment, complementing a gap in the health area.

The execution design of the device focuses on the dynamics of the wrist/hand member which comprises degrees of freedom characteristic of the limb. The constant search for improvements, leads to find the existing gaps in the equipment of the current genre that seek to help in the rehabilitation and treatment of the wrist. The design device aims above all to not cause data on the recovering member, so the selected engine is a low torque motor, enabling it to perform angular movements at low speeds and with low applied forces. The associated movements are of angular movements, achieving the different degrees of freedom associated with the wrist, through the mechanical dynamics that the support allows.

The elaborated equipment underwent some validation tests, among them the ones of analysis of forces and consumptions, continuing with a comparison with the data provided. Speed variation tests were also performed, evaluating the torque/speed/power ratio, thus verifying optimum points or peaks of motor forces and currents. Further tests should be performed in order to analyze other properties, such as rehabilitation and proprioception user improvements properties.

Keywords: Rehabilitation, Proprioception, Control

DEVELOPMENT OF A PORTABLE ENDOSCOPY DEVICE WITH IMPROVED IMAGE QUALITY

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ABSTRACT

This article presents the development of a novel portable endoscopy device designed to enhance image quality while maintaining user-friendliness and portability. Traditional endoscopy systems are often bulky and require extensive setup, which can hinder their use in emergency and outpatient settings.

Our innovative device integrates advanced imaging technology, including high-definition cameras and improved light sources, to provide clearer and more detailed visuals during examinations. The design process involved a comprehensive analysis of existing endoscopic tools, identifying key limitations in image resolution, mobility, and ease of use. We employed a modular design approach, enabling the device to be easily assembled and disassembled, which facilitates maintenance and upgrades. Rigorous testing was conducted in various clinical scenarios, demonstrating significant improvements in image quality compared to conventional devices.

The portable endoscope not only offers high-definition imagery but also features wireless connectivity, allowing for real-time data sharing and remote consultations with specialists. Feedback from healthcare professionals highlighted the device's ergonomic design and intuitive controls, making it suitable for both trained endoscopists and novice users.

This development has the potential to expand access to endoscopic procedures, particularly in under-resourced areas where traditional systems are impractical. Overall, the portable endoscopy device represents a significant advancement in the field of medical imaging, promising to improve diagnostic capabilities and patient outcomes.

Keywords: Portable endoscopy, image quality, medical imaging, device development, high-definition cameras, wireless connectivity, clinical applications.

ISO 9000 AS A TOOL FOR ENHANCING CUSTOMER SATISFACTION IN SERVICE COMPANIES

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ABSTRACT

In today's competitive service industry, maintaining high levels of customer satisfaction is crucial for business success. The ISO 9000 series of standards offers a comprehensive framework for quality management, helping service companies optimize their processes, improve reliability, and enhance customer feedback mechanisms. This article explores how ISO 9000 contributes to improving customer satisfaction by standardizing processes, fostering continuous improvement, and systematically managing customer feedback.

Key mechanisms of ISO 9000, such as process standardization and the Plan-Do-Check-Act (PDCA) cycle, allow companies to ensure consistent service delivery, which builds customer trust and loyalty. By implementing standardized procedures, companies reduce the likelihood of errors and deliver a more reliable customer experience.

Feedback management, another integral aspect of ISO 9000, ensures that companies gather and analyze customer input effectively, leading to faster resolutions and proactive improvements. Real-world examples illustrate how ISO 9000 has positively impacted service companies.

Key words: ISO 9000, Customer satisfaction, Quality management, Service companies, Process standardization, Continuous improvement, Feedback management, PDCA cycle, Service quality, Operational efficiency, Customer loyalty.

IMPROVING THE CONTROL'S QUALITY OF IMPORTED GOODS FOR THE PRESENCE OF FORBIDDEN ITEMS

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ABSTRACT

This article introduces a forward-thinking methodology aimed at improving the efficiency and accuracy of import control for prohibited substances, addressing key limitations in

traditional border security practices. Current methods often depend on manual observation and basic monitoring, which struggle to keep up with the high volume of travelers and goods, leading to slower processing times and potential security gaps.

The proposed approach combines facial recognition with advanced artificial intelligence (AI) to analyze passenger behavior patterns in real time. CCTV cameras strategically positioned in control zones continuously capture passenger movements, which are then analyzed by AI algorithms to detect any deviations from normal behavior. Nervous gestures, erratic walking, or hesitation can indicate concealed intent or illicit activities. By flagging behavioral anomalies early, the system helps customs officers identify potentially high-risk individuals more efficiently.

Once flagged, these individuals undergo a thorough inspection process involving technologies like X-ray scanning, odor sensors, and ion mobility spectrometry (IMS). X-ray scanners reveal the contents of luggage, odor sensors detect specific scents associated with prohibited substances, and IMS performs sensitive chemical analysis. Together, these tools create a multi-layered inspection process that reinforces the initial AI screening, effectively catching contraband that could evade simpler checks.

A critical benefit of this approach is the AI's ability to consolidate data from each inspection tool into a unified information system. This integrated view allows customs operators to access real-time insights, improving the speed and accuracy of decision-making. By equipping officers with comprehensive profiles and alerts, the system reduces inspection times and enables better risk management at checkpoints.

In summary, this method marks a significant advancement in border security. By integrating modern data analysis with AI-driven behavioral assessment, the system enhances import control, combining efficiency with precision and setting a new standard for border technology.

Keywords: image recognition, artificial intelligence, x-ray scanning, odor sensor, suspicious recognizing.

IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF POWER SUPPLY SYSTEM OF ARTIFICIAL URINARY SPINCTER

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ABSTRACT

Long-term power management is crucial for biomedical implants, particularly for devices like the artificial urinary sphincter (AUS) AMS800, which aids in restoring urinary control for patients with incontinence. Traditional implants typically use non-rechargeable batteries that, once depleted, require surgical replacement. This process not only raises healthcare costs but also poses risks to the patient, introducing discomfort and potential complications associated with repeated surgeries. To address these limitations, this work

explores wireless inductive charging as a sustainable alternative for recharging implantable devices. Using principles of magnetic resonance, power is transferred through an external transmitter coil placed near the skin, which creates an electromagnetic field. This field induces current in a receiver coil implanted with the AUS device, wirelessly recharging its battery.

A key component in this system is the adaptive voltage doubler/rectifier (VD/REC), which optimizes the power transfer process by adjusting its mode based on coil misalignment and other variations in positioning. This feature stabilizes energy transfer, making it possible to recharge the implant effectively even when the coil alignment fluctuates. The VD/REC's adaptability helps maintain efficient power conversion, maximizing transmission efficiency even with distances and orientations that may not always be ideal. Studies on transmission efficiency show that a carefully configured system, using resonant frequencies such as 13.56 MHz, can achieve up to 80% efficiency at optimal transmission distances. By eliminating the need for surgical battery replacements, wireless inductive charging for the AMS800 enhances patient comfort and safety, providing a reliable and non-invasive solution for powering bio-implants. This technology represents a significant advancement in medical device design, with the potential for broad applications across various implantable devices, including cardiac pacemakers and other bio-actuators, ultimately reducing patient risk and healthcare costs.

Keywords: biomedical implants, AMS800, wireless power transfer, battery recharging, power management.

ISO 50001 ENERGY MANAGEMENT: UNLOCKING ENERGY EFFICIENCY POTENTIAL IN AZERBAIJAN

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ABSTRACT

ISO 50001 provides a valuable framework for organizations looking to enhance energy management, leading to cost reductions and improved energy efficiency. In Azerbaijan, where energy demand continues to grow, there is significant potential for optimizing energy consumption across various sectors. This article looks at the opportunities and challenges of adopting ISO 50001 in Azerbaijan, particularly in industries where effective energy management can make a big difference.

The benefits of implementing ISO 50001 are clear. Organizations can see reduced energy usage, cost savings, and an increased commitment to sustainability. However, several challenges may affect how well this framework can be applied. For instance, existing regulatory structures might complicate the adoption of standardized energy practices, and economic constraints could limit the necessary investments for implementing energy-efficient measures. Additionally, there is a need to develop technical expertise in energy management, as local skills are still growing.

To address these obstacles, Azerbaijan can learn from international examples where ISO 50001 has been successfully implemented. Creating supportive government policies that promote energy efficiency and fostering cooperation with the private sector can help

create an environment conducive to adopting ISO standards. For example, offering financial incentives, such as tax breaks or grants for organizations that adopt energy management systems, could stimulate interest and participation. Furthermore, investing in training programs for professionals in energy management will help build local expertise.

By taking these actions, Azerbaijan can move toward more sustainable energy use, benefiting both its economy and the environment. With the adoption of ISO 50001, the country can achieve significant energy savings, lower its carbon footprint, and work towards broader goals of energy security and sustainable development. This proactive approach not only aligns with global trends but also positions Azerbaijan as a committed participant in international efforts to enhance energy efficiency and address climate change.

Keywords: ISO 50001, Barriers to energy efficiency, Azerbaijan energy sector, Energy management, Energy efficiency

ENERGY PERFORMANCE OF BUILDINGS DIRECTIVE (EPBD) IN THE EU: A ROADMAP FOR AZERBAIJAN

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ABSTRACT

The Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) is a critical EU policy aimed at increasing energy efficiency in buildings to reach climate neutrality by 2050. This directive sets nearly-zero energy standards for new constructions, encourages efficient renovations, and enforces the use of Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) for transparency on energy usage. Through the integration of renewable energy and systematic monitoring, the EPBD aims to reduce both energy expenses and greenhouse gas emissions across the EU. For Azerbaijan, which aims to enhance energy security and reduce fossil fuel reliance, adopting EPBD principles presents an opportunity to boost the energy efficiency of its buildings. Yet, successful implementation will require an approach that considers Azerbaijan's distinct climate, infrastructure, and economic context. This could include prioritizing energy-efficient design for new buildings, updating existing structures to improve efficiency, and introducing an EPC system to monitor energy consumption and encourage property upgrades.

Azerbaijan could also benefit from awareness campaigns on energy-saving practices and financial incentives, like grants or tax breaks, to support energy-efficient renovations and renewable energy adoption in the building sector. Solar and wind energy integration, for

instance, would reduce pressure on conventional energy sources while advancing the country's energy security and sustainability goals.

By adapting EPBD-aligned policies, Azerbaijan could achieve significant energy savings, lessen environmental impacts, and advance its climate goals. These improvements would contribute to Azerbaijan's sustainable development strategy and align its practices with global standards on climate action. Through tailored building standards and energy-efficient practices, Azerbaijan has the potential to create a more sustainable future, reinforcing its commitment to reducing environmental impacts and supporting long-term energy resilience. This approach not only strengthens Azerbaijan's national objectives but also aligns with broader global efforts toward environmental responsibility and climate adaptation.

Keywords: Energy Performance of Buildings Directive, Environmental sustainability, Building sector renovation, Energy Performance Certificates, Greenhouse gas emissions

NEW PRINCIPLES OF INTELLIGENT CONTROL-MEASUREMENT AND CONTROL SYSTEMS DESIGN FOR A GREEN FUTURE

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ABSTRACT

Since it is an urgent issue to maintain the ecological balance of nature and to carry out continuous, multiple monitoring for the sake of "Green future", the issues of development and real application of smart control-measurement and control systems with high measurement accuracy and reliability are considered. Mainly, full automation of crop growing processes in different areas of agriculture: ventilation, irrigation, high-precision distribution of minerals, heating, in short, complex control of parameters and other important issues were involved in the research.

Drones are being used significantly in modern agricultural facilities, especially in difficult, densely vegetated areas, giving farmers new opportunities to increase productivity and reduce costs. With the help of drones, farmers can collect real information about the current situation in the fields, at the same time early detection of diseases in plants, maturity period and other factors (current situations) can be determined. Smart sensors and multispectral cameras installed on drones provide high resolutions, and thanks to their payload capabilities, accurate 3D models are obtained, photos and vegetation maps are formed by species. Thanks to the application of such a system, the farmland, its vegetation, and its yield are regularly monitored, and as a result, farm planning becomes much easier. Visual control of vegetation cover, soil moisture, air temperature, humidity,

oxygen richness, lighting level, etc. through drones. general monitoring is planned for the entire area.

As a result of the systematic approach, there is a need to develop a multi-parameter and multi-functional intelligent control-measurement and control system. At this time, in order to obtain high accuracy in measurement results, continuous monitoring of all measuring devices is carried out, and hybrid test measurement algorithms, basic test equations and different structures are built to improve their measurement accuracy. As a result, lossless collection and processing of useful information and, ultimately, making correct management decisions are realized. In addition to all this, an automated calibration operation is carried out to ensure the stability and reliability of the metrological characteristics of the operating control-measuring devices.

As you can see, the reviewed studies are new approaches, and as a result, the designed system is of special relevance, scientific and practical importance. The intelligent control-measurement and management system developed on the basis of smart technologies was actually applied in tomato cultivation in a closed greenhouse environment with certain limitations, efficiency and productivity increased.

Keywords. agriculture, vegetation, monitoring, intelligence, control, measurement, management

USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE FOR A SUSTAINABLE GREEN FUTURE

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the challenges and opportunities involved in integrating artificial intelligence (AI) into initiatives aimed at fostering a sustainable, environmentally-conscious future. It starts by outlining the United Nations' key sustainability standards, which serve as a framework for promoting eco-friendly practices and guiding the development of green technologies. The piece then examines AI's role in advancing environmentally sustainable technologies and creating "smart" systems. A sustainable future depends on the efficient management of natural resources, and urgent global issues such as climate change, resource depletion, and pollution require immediate action.

Green technologies are critical in addressing these concerns by minimizing the human impact on the environment. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) emphasize the importance of global cooperation to enhance human well-being and protect the planet. These goals aim to eradicate poverty, boost economic growth, improve education, healthcare, and social protection, and combat climate change. Green technologies focus

on reducing waste, lowering greenhouse gas emissions, enhancing energy efficiency, and developing renewable energy sources to help mitigate environmental harm. Integrating AI into green technologies presents new opportunities, advancing the development of innovative solutions for environmental challenges. AI's potential to enhance the effectiveness of sustainable technologies can lead to a more sustainable and resource-efficient future. By combining AI with environmental efforts, intelligent systems are developed to optimize energy use, reduce emissions, and improve waste management. This collaboration promises to drive progress toward a sustainable global future, offering creative and effective solutions to the world's most urgent environmental problems. The synergy between AI and green technologies thus holds great promise for accelerating efforts to combat climate change and protect the planet.

Keyword: Sustainable future, green technologies, smart objects, artificial intelligence.

AUTOMATED AUDITING OF FUTURE-PROOF SECURITY STANDARDS OF BIG DATA-BASED SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

The theme of this article is SCAP (Security Content Automation Protocol) technology. It is the central part of information security in modern times and it is also connected with other basic securities. SCAP is a group of protocols and tools which are standardized and used to assess, monitor, and report the security status of IT infrastructure.

The study of the relevant components of SCAP, including sub-protocols such as CVE, CCE, CPE, and OVAL, and their functions is analyzed in the article. The use from a practical point of view of the SCAP tool, such as vulnerability detection, configuration management and compliance control gets discussed. Particularly, the common points of SCAP with international standards like ISO 27001 are dealt with in detail. The article researches how SCAP can contribute to compliance with the 27001 requirements, especially in the fields of risk management, asset management and security control[1]. The paper also focuses on the integration of SCAP with other frameworks such as the NIST Cybersecurity Framework and PCI DSS. The thesis is based on the use of SCAP as a tool that standardizes and automates the security processes. It is pointed out that this bit of technology may thus bring about efficient and effective IT security management. However, the challenges and the limitations of SCAP implementation are also considered. The article features new chapters on the future of SCAP technology and the increasing use its development will receive in the realm of information safety, the importance of this technology and the potential directions a future investigative research could take. Besides, the paper talks about the use of SCAP in conjunction with other standards, which, in turn, brings about a better security situation for organizations.

Keywords: SCAP, XCCDF, CVE, OpenSCAP, OVAL

PERSONNEL MANAGEMENT AND MOTIVATION IN THE ENTERPRISE

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ABSTRACT

The emergence and development of the industrial revolution in the 18th century revealed a number of problems related to the systematization and increasing the efficiency of manual labor in factories. The research conducted by "Forbes" magazine in the world's first 500 industrial organizations showed that 97% of these organizations have annual plans related to "Work motivation of personnel". Studies also show that after the implementation of the standards developed and published by the International Organization for Standardization, the motivation and efficiency of the employees of the enterprise increases significantly, and in this regard, the income increases proportionally. "Forbes" magazine's research on the world's top 500 industrial organizations showed that 97% of these companies have annual plans for "Personnel motivation".

The annual plans for increasing motivation in these institutions include the following:

- assignment of duties according to employees' knowledge and skills,
- qualification and periodic training of employees according to their duties;
- materially evaluating the quality of the work done by the employees, etc.

The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) has given extensive space in several of its published standards related to the effective operation of personnel in enterprises and the elimination of possible problems.

Keywords: personnel management, quality management, risk management, standard, management, motivation.

IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF EXPERIMENTAL RESEARCH IN GASLIFT OIL EXTRACTION

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ABSTRACT

As oil fields are developed, a gradual reduction in reservoir pressure eventually makes the fountain method of well operation no longer feasible. Consequently, the gas lift method is frequently chosen as a viable alternative. Like many other technological processes, the operation of wells using the gas lift method is influenced by a variety of factors. These factors often result in a decline in well productivity, operational inefficiencies, and sometimes accidents. Due to the dynamic nature of the process and its specific characteristics, continuous assessment and adjustment of the optimal operating conditions for gas lift wells are required through thorough research.

The data gathered from these experimental investigations are essential for defining the key operational parameters of the wells. However, altering operating conditions and taking necessary measurements during research can lead to non-productive losses. Additionally, the challenge of ensuring that the data is both accurate and reliable remains a major concern. In light of stricter regulations governing oil extraction and an increased emphasis on economic efficiency, improving operational effectiveness has become a top priority.

In order to achieve the set goal, the solution of the following issues is envisaged:

1. Development of mathematical models and algorithms for increasing the efficiency of experimental researches, appropriate database for conducting these types of researches ensuring obtaining data with acceptable accuracy;
2. Improving and researching the structure of management and control systems that ensure the efficiency of experiments; improving the management of passive experiments;
3. Determining the optimal plan and sequence of experiments;
4. Computer simulation and study of developed algorithms and models, as well as structures;

Keywords: Gaslift wells, Experimental studies, Mathematical model, Oil extraction process

Development of microcontroller protection device of power transformers

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ABSTRACT

Protection of power transformers is a very complex problem in the transmission system of the power system. Since it is very important to minimize the frequency and duration of unwanted interruptions, this is a high demand placed on power transformer protective relays. Various transfer principles have been proposed and used to protect transformers from various types of faults. Relays that use the principles of overcurrent, overcurrent and overheat protect transformers from overload and external applied conditions. Differential relays protect against internal transformer failure. In this study, the software and hardware of the microcontroller-based relay system were explained and designed, and the system design and testing were also presented.

Power transformers are very expensive and vital components in electrical power systems. They sometimes suffer from disturbances caused by atmospheric disturbances and transient waves. These faults include internal, that is, faults between parts of the coils, external, that is, external short circuits, overvoltage, overcurrent.

This work describes the design and implementation of a microcontroller based system to protect a power transformer. The system includes devices for internal fault current, magnetizing current, differential protection, overcurrent protection, overvoltage protection and undervoltage protection.

In this article, the design of a microcontroller based relay for power transformer protection will be considered. Percentage differential protection, overcurrent and external fault protection, overvoltage and undervoltage protection have been implemented. In the first quarter of the primary current, the rate of change of primary current versus time method is adopted to separate the internal faults of the primary current wave from the current, which depends on the high differential effect of the magnetizing current wave.

Power system protection is a very important issue in electric power system design. Electrical power components must be protected from dangerous faults. This is driven by the need to increase component life, avoid unnecessary costs, replace worn components infrequently, and ensure a continuous power supply to serve the needs of an ever-growing economy. Therefore this project attempts to design a microcontroller based system that will intelligently monitor faults and offer a safety measure to protect the power transformer in case of power overload.

The microcontroller relay has real-time data monitoring, abnormal condition detection, and fast processing speed. The microcontroller relay acts as a multi-function relay. Thus, it further reduces installation costs and maintenance costs. Microcontroller relay is the latest development for all types of faults. So, a microcontroller-based relay is used to protect the power transformer.

Correct acceptance and operation of protective relays requires fairly accurate reproduction of abnormal and normal conditions in the power system. This information enters power systems usually through a Current Transformer and a Voltage Transformer.

Keywords: Power transformer protection, starting current, differential protection, current transformer, voltage transformer, interest differential protection

COMBINED ANALYTICAL DEVICE BASED ON THE THERMAL EFFECT OF THE "COLD FLAME" OXIDATION REACTION

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ABSTRACT

Based on experimental studies of the oxidation reaction modes of substances with ozone-containing gas under cold flame conditions, the possibilities of creating a combined analytical device based on a thermal conductivity detector for the qualitative and quantitative analysis of substances are considered. The proposed combined analytical device allows to identify different hydrocarbons belonging to various homological series. The results of experimental studies of the combined analytical device, the operation principle of which is based on the conversion of the thermal effect of the reaction of ozone-containing gas with substances into an information measuring signal, are presented. The results of experimental studies of the combined analytical device based on this principle are presented. Under otherwise identical conditions, due to the dependence of the detector signal characteristics on the nature of the analyzed substance, the dependence of the detector's measurement signal on the volume of the analyzed substance dose, as well as on various values of the current applied to the detector, the flow rates of the carrier gas and the ozone-containing gas, are studied. The feasibility of determining the group composition of mixtures of liquid hydrocarbons has been analysed, which makes it possible to approach the solution of the most important problem of analytical control of light oil products from a new perspective. The combined analytical device developed on the basis of a thermal conductivity detector can be used both as a thermal conductivity detector and a thermochemical detector under the same operating mode parameters and as a selective ozonolysis detector when the operating mode parameters are adjusted. Experimental studies were carried out using standard units of laboratory chromatograph and ozonisation unit included in the ozonator, which does not require air or water cooling and allows ozone synthesis.

Keywords: Combined device, thermal conductivity detector, thermochemical detector, ozonator, ozone, atomic oxygen, concentration.

REVIEW OF INTELLIGENT SOLAR ENERGY PROGNOSTICS SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

There is an increasing interest in forecasting and optimizing the utilization of solar energy owing to its recognition as a clean source of energy and renewable energy resource. Therefore it is very important to build intelligent systems capable not only of forecasting the potential energy production but also capable of ensuring reliability and maintenance of solar installations. The abstract provides a systematic analysis on the development of intelligent diagnostic systems of solar installations and the integration of machine learning, data science and artificial intelligence in predicting solar radiation, energy production and performance of solar components. Such systems are intended to address short range operational weather dependent solar energy generation as well as long range solar energy generation and supply operational sustainability under varying conditions. An area of concern which was dealt with is the latent capability of these systems to estimate the future degradation or failure of solar panels based on sensor readings, thus allowing corrective action to be taken before the situation gets worse, hence reducing system downtime and eliminating expensive breakdowns. The maintenance of these assets is much less expensive and much less problematic since the unforeseen failures are avoided, rather maintenance is performed proactively in a predictive manner. The review brings out a need to incorporate predictive analytics in solar power monitoring with solar energy systems management for further efficient performance and the long-term viability of such systems. Besides maintenance and forecasting, the review examines the possible AI solar energy management systems that may be added to those already available in the near future. Transitions should include the use of complex AI woven machines such as deep learning and reinforcement learning ones which are able to learn and change in accordance with environmental requirements effectively improving solar generation and storage. The paper also discusses the challenges that current solar energy systems face, arguing for newer AI algorithms to tackle the evolving complexity of modern-day installs and offer better forecasts. With the space of intelligent solar energy systems growing, AI and machine learning are undoubtedly going to be integrally fundamental for sustainable power management. Such developments not only upgrade the management and productivity of solar power systems, but also exponentially contribute to reducing reliance on non-renewable energy resources in favor of global environmental preservation.

Keywords: intelligent systems, solar energy, prognostics, AI in prognostics, Renewable energy.

FEATURES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF DEVICES BASED ON RENEWABLE ENERGY IN BIOMEDICAL ENGINEERING

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ABSTRACT

The development of mobile technologies, micro- and nanotechnologies and the use of these technologies in biomedical engineering contributed to the intellectualization of portable and wearable medical devices, and also created the basis for wide distribution in the field of ensuring human health. These smart devices, helping people to conduct a healthier life, provide them with constant medical monitoring of physiological parameters in real time, which gives the necessary information flow to control the metabolic state, for the diagnosis and treatment of diseases. Modern implantable medical devices are capable of replacing the most important functions of the human body. They can be successfully used to support heart function or to help people with complete hearing loss, to treat chronic pain syndrome and to solve many other critical problems. For these devices to function, there is a need for electrical power sources. Traditional methods, depending on the type of device, require the transmission of energy from an external source via wires through the patient's skin or require the installation of a battery in the patient's body. Both approaches have significant drawbacks: in the first case, there is a risk of life-threatening infections, and in the second case, the need for repeated battery replacement. Therefore, it now makes perfect sense to deliver energy to these devices wirelessly (wireless power transmission - WPT). However, the development and implementation of WPT systems with high energy transfer efficiency requires solving a number of complex problems. When designing WPT systems, key parameters such as the size of the system, the distance between the medical device implanted in the body and the external environment, the operating frequency, and the safety of the dissipated energy for tissues should be considered almost in conflict. In addition, it should be noted that WPT systems can create magnetic fields that can potentially affect the health of surrounding living organisms and the operation of nearby electronic devices. The purpose of the article is to conduct a comparative analysis of the progress achieved in the field of WPT systems and wearable medical devices in recent decades and the selection of adequate systems for specific applications. The paper describes WPT wireless energy transmission systems, such as capacitive, inductive, magnetic resonance, ultrasonic, optical, triboelectric, thermoelectric, etc., and presents their advantages and disadvantages.

Keywords: implanted medical devices, wearable medical devices, wireless energy systems, mobile technologies, micro-nanotechnology.

MODELING OF ENVIRONMENTAL MONITORING SYSTEM OF OIL PUMPING STATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Oil pumping stations consist of a complex system of modules necessary for the efficient operation of an enterprise engaged in processing, storing or collecting petroleum products. This system may include pumps, receiving, starting and cleaning facilities, feeder and distribution networks of oil pipelines, diagnostic equipment, service elements, and storage tanks. The main function of pumping stations is to create the necessary pressure for normal transportation of petroleum products and maintain the pressure level throughout the entire period of operation. The oil and gas industry plays an important role in the global economy, but it also poses serious environmental risks. Pumping stations needed to transport crude oil from production sites to refineries can pollute the surrounding ecosystem with petroleum products as a result of leaks, overflows or equipment malfunctions. Therefore, continuous environmental monitoring is an urgent task for the timely detection of any potential hazard in the pumping station network.

The objective of the work is to design and simulate an automated environmental monitoring system based on modern sensors for oil pumping stations to minimize harmful impact on the environment and ensure operational safety. Environmental monitoring systems for oil pumping stations are important for timely detection, prediction and, consequently, prevention of environmental hazards and accidents arising during oil production, transportation and refining. Design and modeling of these systems requires an approach that includes elements of environmental science, engineering and information technology. The paper presents a multifunctional model of the environmental monitoring system for oil pumping stations with an emphasis on key components such as sensor networks, data collection, signal processing and decision-making algorithms. The proposed model emphasizes the integration of real-time monitoring, preventive maintenance and sustainable practices, which are vital to ensure environmental safety and regulatory compliance. The paper investigates potential environmental risks of oil pumping stations, identifies components of environmental monitoring systems for oil pumping stations, develops an algorithm for the system model, and considers information security issues. The construction of the system model includes the following stages: defining the requirements for the system in accordance with the controlled environmental parameter and selecting the appropriate sensors; specifying the locations of the sensors; selecting algorithms for the system's operation in real time, taking into account the complexity of environmental risks and the capabilities of the equipment used. The system also integrates decision-making and signaling subsystems, as well as preventive maintenance algorithms.

Keywords: environmental monitoring, oil pumping stations, sensor networks, preventive maintenance, real-time monitoring, environmental parameters.

ECOLOGICAL MATERIALS FOR BIOMEDICAL IMPLANTS

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ABSTRACT

Biomedical implants have revolutionized modern medicine, improving the quality of life of millions of people by providing solutions for replacing, recovery, or connecting damaged or diseased tissues. Of great importance are the applications of implants in orthopedics, dentistry, cardiovascular system, hearing loss treatment, nerve stimulators, and other fields. However, traditional materials used to manufacture biomedical implants often face problems of biocompatibility, environmental issues, and durability. Materials traditionally used for implants include metals such as titanium and stainless steel, and synthetic polymers such as silicone and polyethylene. Although these materials have favorable mechanical properties and durability, they have limitations such as poor biocompatibility, risk of rejection by the body, and adverse environmental impacts during production and disposal. Currently, in view of increasing attention to environmental protection, the scientific community is constantly synthesizing and comprehensively researching environmentally friendly materials for biomedical implants. These materials, derived from natural or renewable sources, have the potential to reduce healthcare's carbon footprint by promoting biodegradation without losing functionality.

The aim of this paper is to study the current trends in the development and application of green technology-based materials for biomedical implants, analyze their advantages and challenges, and provide proposals to justify the selection of suitable materials for future work in bioimplant engineering. It should be noted that the biological environment does not fully accept the implanted material. Therefore, implants should be selected in such a way as to optimize biological performance and minimize adverse biological response while maintaining adequate function.

This paper reviews various green materials such as biodegradable polymers, ceramics, and plant-based compounds, as well as nanocellulose, which are considered promising materials for the development of durable biomedical implants.

The integration of environmentally sustainable materials into biomedical implants holds great promise for the future of healthcare. With advances in materials science and engineering, biodegradable polymers, ceramics, and plant-based composites may become viable alternatives to traditional implant materials. However, further research is needed to overcome the technical and regulatory barriers associated with these materials.

Key words. biomedical implant, environmentally friendly biomaterials, polymers, ceramics, nanocellulose.

METROLOGY AND LEGAL BASIS FOR ENSURING THE UNIFORMITY OF MEASUREMENTS

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the role of metrology and legal support for the uniformity of measurement. It considers the importance of metrology as a science of measurements, specifies the basic terms and principles, such as calibration, verification and use of standards. It also emphasizes the importance of national legislation and international standards in ensuring the comparability of measurements at the global level. The study aims to identify key points that contribute to improving the quality of measurements and increasing confidence in the results, which is fundamental for scientific research and practice.

Metrology is a field of activity whose fundamental provisions must be enshrined in law, adopted in accordance with the legislation of the country. This is due to the fact that all legal norms aimed at protecting the rights and legitimate interests of consumers must be regulated by legislative acts adopted by the supreme legislative body of the country. Legislation in the field of metrology must promote the economic and social development of the country by protecting against the negative consequences of unreliable measurement results.

Activities to ensure the uniformity of measurements (UEM) are carried out in accordance with:

- The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Metrology", adopted in 1993;
- By decrees of the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Today, metrological activity in our republic is regulated by the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Metrology". It follows that metrological activity is included in the general system of law and, on the one hand, has its own specific norms, and on the other hand, must closely interact with the general system of public administration and the state system of generally binding norms.

Ensuring the uniformity of measurements is also the task of various international metrology organizations. As an example, two of the largest international metrology organizations are briefly considered below.

International Organization of Weights and Measures (IOWM) is an intergovernmental organization that includes the International Bureau of Weights and Measures (BIPM), whose main task is the storage, improvement and comparison of national and

international standards, improvement of the metric system of measurements, etc. For example, the adoption of the international system of units (SI), a new definition of the second and the meter.

International Organization of Legal Metrology (OIML) established in 1956., unites more than 80 countries. Its goal is to develop general issues of legal metrology: establishing accuracy classes of measuring Instrumentations, the procedure for verifying and calibrating measuring Instrumentations, harmonizing methods of comparison, verification and certification of standards, developing optimal forms of organizing metrological services, etc.

The technical basis of the State Standards Institute is the state standard base, concentrated in the Center of National Standards (CNE) of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The main scientific and practical center is the Research Institute of Standardization, Metrology and Certification (NIISMS).

Coordination of work and general technical guidance in the field of ensuring the uniformity of measurements in the Republic of Uzbekistan is carried out by the Metrology Department of the Uzbek Agency for Technical Regulation.

Keywords: metrology, calibration of measuring Instrumentations, legal basis, ensuring the uniformity of measurements, national legislation.

ASSESSMENT OF UNCERTAINTY IN NITROGEN MEASUREMENTS UNDER CONDITIONS OF INSUFFICIENT INFORMATION IN ENVIRONMENTAL STUDIES. THE IMPACT OF NITROGEN OXIDES ON ENVIRONMENTAL QUALITY

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ABSTRACT

In the context of limited information, uncertainty assessment of nitrogen measurements is an important task in environmental studies. Nitrogen oxides (NO_x), including nitric oxide (NO) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), play a key role in environmental quality, as they contribute to smog and oxygen deficiency, and negatively affect human health and ecosystems. In the conditions of a lack of information and a huge variety of factors influencing the level of nitrogen content in the environment, the assessment of the uncertainty of measurements becomes a critically important task in ecology. Nitrogen oxides (NO_x), such as nitrogen oxide (NO) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), not only actively participate in the processes of photochemical pollution, but also contribute to the formation of secondary pollutants, such as ozone at the level of the earth's surface, which significantly worsens air quality and negatively affects human health and ecosystems. This article discusses methods for estimating uncertainty in nitrogen measurements that consider the influence of various factors, such as data quality, monitoring methods, and variability of natural conditions. An analysis of the studies shows that the use of statistical

methods allows for a more accurate assessment of the level of pollution and its impact on ecosystems. The studies highlight the importance of integrating NO_x monitoring into environmental strategies to make informed decisions to improve environmental quality and reduce negative impacts on public health. Additionally, an important aspect is the study of long-term trends in concentrations of nitrogen oxides and their dependence on changes in regulatory policy, such as the introduction of emission standards and the use of cleaner technologies. Understanding these relationships can help in developing effective strategies to reduce emissions and improve air quality. These approaches not only allow for a better understanding of pollution dynamics, but also for more informed predictions of its impact on ecological systems. Thus, the assessment of uncertainty in nitrogen measurements is an integral part of successful environmental quality management, which requires interdisciplinary cooperation and the implementation of modern scientific approaches to minimize the negative impacts of pollution.

Keywords: uncertainty, environment, nitrogen oxides, nitric oxide, nitrogen dioxides, measurement.

Metrological self-check and self-diagnostics in equipment and process monitoring tasks

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ABSTRACT

Industry 4.0 is aimed at the development of digital automated production, including the use of artificial intelligence. The level of digitalization essentially affects on production efficiency.

Number of accidents on factories in first quartile of digitalization in 3 times less then in forth quartile. Reliability of the equipment higher on 4%. In first quartile it demand, half the maintenance cost then in forth quartile. Equipment effectiveness: usage rate is 10% higher in first quartile. Emission of pollutions on 30% less at first quartile power consumption on 30% less also.

That numbers are result of analysis Emerson corporation – the ideologist of digital industry.

Good results cannot be achieved without timely and reliable information on process parameters. The system receives these data from numerous sensors. Reliability that information can provide **Metrological self-checking (MSC)**.

Metrological self-checking is a procedure that automatically assesses the level of uncertainty of measuring Instrumentations. That method was first proposed in 1985 by the Mendeleev State Scientific Center, the leading metrological center in Russia.

Another important term is **Self-diagnostics**. It implies the automatic detection defects of equipment. The trend towards the advancement of automated production is a combination of **Metrological self-checking** and **technical Self-diagnostics**.

Self-diagnostics is widespread not only in production systems. It also used in biological and social systems. The most significant stages in the development of biological systems were those that led to an increase in system viability. According to Nobel laureate Ilya Prigozhin, "Self-development in nature occurs through the destruction of non-viable forms." In these cases, metrological self-checking, reflects the body's ability to detect threats to the normal functioning of its systems and transmit information on the threat to the components of the body that can limit this threat. According to N. Wiener's theory, these sensors provide information and the animal's brain processes it, which increases survival, both now and in the long term.

IMEKO (International Measurement Confederation) is an important social system than collects, analyzes, and discusses scientific information at symposia's and congresses. Technical committees make self-diagnostic condition of research and determine direction of development. IMEKO is essential for the development of measurement and metrology science.

Self-diagnostics in cold steel rolling systems have strong analogy with biological systems.

Keywords: Metrological self-control, self-diagnosis, monitoring, technical equipment, technological processes.

SYSTEM FOR MONITORING THE LEVEL OF ELECTROMAGNETIC RADIATION BASED ON RENEWABLE ENERGY

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ABSTRACT

The environment is affected by electromagnetic waves emitted by our widely used electronic devices, communication networks, power lines and other industrial equipment. Electromagnetic radiation (EMR) is a major environmental factor that negatively affects both human health and ecosystems. Chronic exposure to EMF above the permissible level can lead to potential long-term health problems in humans, such as sleep disorders, stress and even cancer. As the world's population increasingly uses wireless technologies and powerful electrical systems, the issue of constant and ubiquitous EMF monitoring is becoming relevant. Currently, wireless sensor networks are preferred in remote monitoring systems. The objective of this work is to develop a system for monitoring electromagnetic radiation levels powered by renewable energy sources and operating on

the basis of Internet of Things (IoT) technologies. We used a solar panel + battery system as a renewable energy source. In this article, monitoring of both the EMR measurement system and the solar cell + battery system is considered. The design of the presented electromagnetic radiation monitoring system consists of three main components: a network of EMR detection sensors, a renewable energy source, and a data collection and transmission unit. The network of electromagnetic radiation sensors includes broadband EMR detectors. These detectors are designed to measure radiation in various frequency ranges, including radio frequency, microwave, and industrial frequency electromagnetic fields. The sensors used must be highly sensitive to weak fields and calibrated according to international standards. To ensure continuous operation of the monitoring system, a battery is connected to the solar cells to power the system in the dark. The system includes a power control unit that ensures efficient distribution and storage of energy between the system components. The data collection and transmission unit operates on a single-board computer and processes data from EMR level sensors in real time and transmits it to the central server via communication modules.

Keywords: Electromagnetic radiation, renewable energy sources, solar energy, environmental monitoring, IoT network.

ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF CLIMATE CHANGE ON THE "FOREST" LANDSCAPE COMPONENT USING THE "DECISION TREE" TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

Climate change is expected to become significantly evident in the coming decades, leading to impacts such as population challenges, hindrances in agricultural development, soil salinization, river depletion, and an increase in natural disasters. Climate, as a fundamental element of environmental factors, plays a critical role in the development of the global economy, and its changes can result in profound socio-economic and political consequences. As a result of various natural and anthropogenic influences, landscape components, water bodies, soil cover, pastures and meadows, agricultural lands, forests, and dense vegetation areas can be damaged. Sudden climate changes are known to have a strong negative impact on the flora and fauna of affected areas. Considering these factors, the analysis of data derived from processing satellite information reflecting abrupt climate variability in various regions of the Republic of Azerbaijan through soft computing methods holds significant scientific and practical

relevance. The article emphasizes the relevance of studying the interdependence of various climate parameters (distribution of solar radiation, air temperature up to two meters in height, soil surface temperature, absolute humidity up to two meters in height, precipitation amount, atmospheric pressure, wind speed at two meters, and relative humidity of the soil surface down to five centimeters) and their impact on landscapes using Artificial Intelligence. In the modern era, soft computing technologies are utilized to solve complex problems of a nature that cannot be addressed by traditional computational methods. Such problems include the analysis of abrupt climate changes. Soft Computing provides tools to manage uncertainties in the real world. Due to its dynamic and multi-dimensional nature, soft computing models serve as invaluable tools for tackling complex real-world problems. They are applied across numerous industrial and research fields. As a result of applying the Decision Tree tool of Artificial Intelligence to the forested areas of the Guba-Khachmaz economic region of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the most influential climate parameters for "Small," "Medium," and "Large" forest areas were identified. The article investigates the impact of certain key climate parameters on the "forest" landscape component of the Guba-Khachmaz economic region using Artificial Intelligence. The analysis utilized the ArcGIS software package, employing data on the areas of the "forest" landscape component (in square kilometers) calculated for the months of July from 1987 to 2022.

Keywords: climate change, landscape, landscape components, forests, artificial intelligence, soft computing, decision tree.

ENSURING CYBERSECURITY OF INFORMATION SYSTEMS IN THE MODERN ERA

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ABSTRACT

Most attacks target people, not technological weaknesses or vulnerabilities. It's time to focus on people with the biggest risk factors. Around 90% of targeted attacks start with email. These are typically phishing attacks: an email purporting to be from an authoritative person or company, and its apparent authenticity convinces the recipient to reveal personal information like passwords or credit card numbers. Most email attacks require the victim to take some action. Since today's attacks target people, defenses must focus on protecting people, educating them, and doing everything possible to avoid being deceived, exploited, or compromised. Over 90% of targeted attacks reach victims via email. The goal of email is to infiltrate the environment and gain access to other important assets. We need multi-layered defenses to:

- Detect known, new, and emerging email attacks

- Take action immediately upon threat detection
- Address both malicious and non-malicious threats
- Protect against spoofed and similar domains.

Effective protection requires the following:

- Continuously evaluate local and global IP addresses to determine if an email connection has been received.
- Recognize potentially malicious emails (such as links to spoofed domains).
- Block emails containing malware from the user block before they reach the recipient's inbox.
- Take evasive measures, such as URL rewriting, to avoid pointing to a malicious site.
- Email to block emails with spoofed sender domains.

When cybercriminals compromise Office 365 credentials, they can launch attacks around you and beyond. They can convince users to transfer money or share sensitive information. And they can access your critical data, such as intellectual property or customer data. Modern, human-centric security aims to protect these accounts from being compromised. Protecting against today's advanced attacks means putting people at the center of your cybersecurity and compliance strategy. But one thing is for sure: they are attacking people, not technology. So we need to shift the focus away from technical exploitation and focus on people. Any organization that takes proactive steps to put people first in its security program is one step ahead of the bad guys.

Keywords: email, targeted attacks, cybersecurity, cybercriminals.

CERTIFICATION AND STANDARDS OF GREEN BUILDINGS IN THE CONSTRUCTION OF BUILDINGS AND COMMERCIAL FACILITIES

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ABSTRACT

Green construction (also referred to as ecological construction) refers to the design, construction, and operation of buildings with minimal environmental impact. Its primary objective is to reduce the consumption of energy and material resources throughout the lifecycle of the building. This encompasses site selection for the design, construction, operation, maintenance, and even demolition of the building.

Another aim of green construction is to preserve or enhance the quality of buildings and to ensure comfort within their interior environments. This form of construction refines traditional building and design practices by incorporating concepts such as efficiency, functionality, durability, and comfort.

Green construction technologies are continuously evolving, with their main purpose being the reduction of the overall environmental and health-related harm caused by buildings.

This is achieved through the following:

- Utilizing energy, water, and other resources more efficiently;
- Prioritizing human health and enhancing workforce productivity;

- Minimizing waste and other environmental impacts.

On a smaller scale, similar approaches are employed in natural construction, which involves the use of local materials.

To identify environmentally sustainable and eco-friendly buildings, green building certifications and standards must be developed. These certifications and standards encompass a wide range of aspects, including the design, construction, operation, and maintenance of buildings.

One of the most widely used green building certifications is the LEED (Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design) certification, developed in the United States. LEED evaluates the sustainability of buildings through a specific rating system designed to minimize their environmental impact.

These standards include ASHRAE 189.1 in the United States and the International Green Building Council (IGBC) Green Building Standards. They address various aspects such as reducing energy and water consumption, utilizing local materials, managing waste, improving indoor air quality, and more.

In the Republic, initiatives are being implemented to encourage the use of alternative energy sources in social facilities and residential buildings. Projects are underway to integrate renewable energy sources into the energy supply of state-funded buildings and social facilities.

Green building standards serve as guidelines aimed at ensuring that buildings are environmentally sustainable and eco-friendly. These standards define best practices that can be applied during the design, construction, operation, and maintenance phases of buildings.

Keywords: green standards, environmental sustainability, green construction, architectural planning, renewable energy.

THE ROLE OF RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES IN AZERBAIJAN

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ABSTRACT

Energy transformation and the use of renewable energy sources are of great importance within the framework of Azerbaijan's "Sustainable Development Goals". In particular, the transition to renewable energy sources is essential to achieve the goals of combating climate change, ensuring energy security and protecting the environment. This helps to maintain economic and ecological balance. The main objective of the thesis is to analyze the role of renewable energy sources (RES) in the energy sector of Azerbaijan and to study the development prospects of this sector. This study emphasizes the importance of

RES for the country's economic, environmental and energy security. At the same time, the existing energy potential and resources in Azerbaijan are assessed, and potential problems and opportunities related to their use are assessed. Azerbaijan has great potential in terms of wind, solar and hydropower sources. In particular, there are favorable conditions for wind energy on the Absheron Peninsula and solar energy in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. The development of renewable energy sources can reduce the country's dependence on energy imports and reduce carbon emissions while maintaining the ecological balance. There are a number of factors that hinder the expansion of renewable energy sources in Azerbaijan. These include the lack of technology and infrastructure, investment requirements and the need to improve the regulatory and legal framework. In order to accelerate the development of renewable energy sources in Azerbaijan, state support, technological innovations and the creation of favorable conditions for investors are essential. At the same time, cooperation with international organizations and investors is important. This thesis provides an in-depth analysis of the development of renewable energy sources in Azerbaijan and the importance of these sources in the country's energy policy. In Azerbaijan, modernization in various sectors of the economy involves increasing environmental sustainability and social well-being. In this context, the use of renewable energy sources is of great importance. In addition to Azerbaijan's rich natural resources, renewable sources such as solar, wind and hydropower play a crucial role in diversifying the country's energy policy and achieving sustainable development. The use of renewable energy sources contributes to the development of technological innovations in Azerbaijan and the creation of new jobs in the energy sector. With the expansion of technologies such as solar panels and wind turbines, the demand for energy storage technologies is increasing. This leads to more efficient use of energy and an increase in the country's technological potential.

Keywords: energy, solar, wind, hydropower, environmental, climate

The Role of Smart Technologies in the Fight Against Climate Change

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ABSTRACT

Climate change is one of the most serious problems humanity faces in the modern era. The rise in global temperatures and the increasing frequency of extreme weather events are creating a growing need for innovative approaches to mitigate these issues. Smart technologies, developed using data, connectivity, and the capabilities of artificial intelligence, play a key role in this fight.

Smart technologies encompass a range of innovative tools and systems that focus on enhancing performance, efficiency, and decision-making through the use of communication and data analytics. Key examples in this field include the Internet of Things (IoT), artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning, big data analytics, and smart grids. These technologies help respond more quickly and informatively to environmental issues by enabling real-time monitoring, predictive analytics, and automation.

In the fight against climate change, smart technologies offer vast opportunities for data collection and analysis. These technologies are used in various fields, ranging from the creation of climate models to ecosystem monitoring. Sensors, satellites, and IoT (Internet of Things) devices are applied for data collection. These devices enable the real-time monitoring of indicators such as air quality, temperature, carbon emissions, and water levels, allowing for the collection of valuable environmental data. Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) methods play a crucial role in the analysis of the collected data. These algorithms process large volumes of data to help predict the impacts of climate change more accurately and take preventive actions. For instance, these technologies are used to assess climate risks and provide early warnings for natural disasters. Thus, smart technologies allow for a deeper approach to climate change and the development of appropriate solutions, while also enhancing efficiency and the ability to respond quickly during the mitigation process. AI and ML increase the ability to predict and solve climate change-related issues by learning complex data relationships. For example, through artificial intelligence, large-scale climate data collected from satellites and other sources can be analyzed. This data is used to assess the impacts of climate change and create new strategies. It also allows for the prediction of how ecosystems will change under various scenarios and when and where extreme weather events will occur.

Keywords: climate, technology, artificial intelligence, energy, forecasting

Air quality monitoring of Baku city and creation of an electronic map

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ABSTRACT

Air pollution indirectly affects the quality of groundwater, soil, vegetation, forests and climate. Cloud precipitation carries air pollutants back to Earth. Acid rain is a prime example of this. Liquid forms of acidic pollutants have been detected in rain, snow, fog, and water vapor. Most acid rain is caused by the oxidation and decomposition of NO_x, SO₂ to nitric acid (HNO₃), sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄).

Poor visibility is also a result of poor air quality, a secondary pollutant and the presence of ground-level ozone, a reaction product between NO_x, a volatile organic compound. During the pandemic, cars were rarely used in Baku, so the peaks of the Caucasus looked like this. The presence of contaminants and suspended particles affects the absorption, secondary emission, reflection or propagation properties of electromagnetic waves at different wavelengths.

The 4th industrial revolution brought not only technical improvements to the life of mankind, but also worsened the general condition of our planet. Pollution of the ocean, land and atmosphere is widespread. The atmosphere of large industrial cities, including Baku, is particularly polluted. The atmosphere of Baku city contains many pollutants. These include dust, sulfur, nitrogen oxides, hydrogen sulfide, carbon monoxide, etc. An air quality index, which includes the calculation of the main pollutants, is used to create an overall picture of the state of the atmosphere, which takes into account the totality of various pollutants. In this regard, in 2013-2014, a measuring complex was created at MAKKA for the purpose of monitoring atmospheric air pollution and drawing up an electronic map in Baku city.

The complex included MX6 iBrid multigas analyzer, ПЗ БП "Atmosphere" sampling probe and other Instrumentations. They were installed on the UAZ car, which made it possible to carry out mobile measurements of the state of the atmosphere. Also, a program was developed to determine the quality of atmospheric air. The program is based on the determination of the concentration of various pollutants and the calculation of a general indicator of air quality - the air pollution index (API). API is the most widely used composite index that takes into account several pollutants and characterizes chronic, long-term air pollution.

Also, the concept of atmospheric pollution and how air pollution affects human health and the state of the environment are shown. An electronic map has been prepared for the monitoring of atmospheric pollution in the city of Baku. The map contains relief layers, terrain descriptions and air pollution. In addition, a module for calculating air quality has been developed. Maps including geomorphological indicators of the monitoring zone are provided.

Key words: atmospheric pollution, electronic map, permissible density limit, atmospheric pollution index

ALTERNATIVE ENERGY SOURCES FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF CREATING A GREEN WORLD

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ABSTRACT

Azerbaijan is one of the countries with high potential for renewable energy sources. Thus, the technical potential of renewable energy sources in our country is 135 GW on land and 157 GW at sea. The economic potential of renewable energy sources is estimated at 27 GW, including 3,000 MW of wind energy, 23,000 MW of solar energy, 380 MW of bioenergy potential, 800 MW of geothermal energy and 520 MW of mountain river potential.

Despite the fact that Azerbaijan is rich in energy resources and is known as an energy exporter in the world, the use of renewable energy sources has always been in the spotlight in the Republic of Azerbaijan. One of the main goals of the energy security policy implemented under the leadership of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Mr. Ilham Aliyev is to strengthen the use of renewable energy sources in our country.

In continuation of the work done in this area, by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated September 22, 2020, No. 1159, the State Agency on Renewable Energy Sources was established under the Ministry of Energy of the Republic of Azerbaijan, and the Fundamentals of the Agency were approved. On May 3, 2021, the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev signed the Decree "On measures related to the creation of the "Green Energy Zone" in the liberated territories of the Republic of Azerbaijan". An agreement was signed between the Ministry of Energy and the Japanese company "TEPCO" to attract a specialized international consulting company to implement the tasks arising from the order, as well as to develop the Concept for the creation of a "Green Energy Zone" in the liberated territories.

By 2045, renewable energy sources such as solar, wind, and geothermal energy will continue to be the fastest growing forms of energy in the global energy mix. Demand for these energy sources will increase by an average of 6.6 percent each year, reaching the equivalent of 25 million barrels of oil per day. At this rate of growth, renewable energy sources will outpace all other forms of energy.

During the reporting period, growth in electricity production will significantly exceed growth in demand for primary energy. Demand for primary energy is expected to grow by an average of 0.9 percent per year. Electricity production will increase by an average of 2.2 percent per year.

Keywords: renewable energy sources, solar energy, wind energy, geothermal energy, technical potential, "Green Energy Zone"

PECULIARITIES OF REGULATION AND STANDARDIZATION OF ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION FROM THE STANDPOINT OF ENVIRONMENTAL PROBLEMS

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ABSTRACT

Information modeling of remote sensing systems requires clarification of issues of standardization of environmental protection activities. A standard is a normative and technical document that establishes a set of norms, rules, requirements that are mandatory for implementation in certain areas of activity.

The system of environmental regulations and standards is determined by practical needs and serves as a tool for solving environmental protection problems. This system includes environmental quality standards, standards for maximum permissible harmful effects on the environment, and environmental standards. The quality standards under consideration form the basis for regulating environmental protection from physical, chemical and biological impacts on the natural environment. When establishing these standards, their scientific validity is taken into account.

At the same time, in a number of cases such documents may be unsuitable or ineffective for ensuring environmental protection, etc.

It is necessary to maintain a balance between financial and material costs and the risk of causing harm to human health and the environment. Within the framework of the development of international environmental law, the activities of the world community in the field of environmental protection are carried out through: rule-making, mutual consultations, environmental monitoring, and control over the state of nature.

Environmental research is a special class of complex tasks due to their multicomponent nature, multivariance, and diversity of the means being assessed. The knowledge gained in the process of analyzing environmental problems allowed them to be transformed into a new technology. An integrated approach to assessing the eco-situation based on a cognitive multimedia monitoring model has been developed. The components of the model are: remote sensing data, contact measurement data, geographic information system, Internet, experts, and the normative and legal base.

Keywords: regulation, standardization, environmental protection, multimedia monitoring model.

CREATING A GREEN WORLD, STANDARTS FOR A RENEWABLE GREEN FUTURE IN ZANGILAN DISTRICT OF EAST ZANGEZUR FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

Various industrial methods, the harmful effects of gases released into the atmosphere, and factors such as the industrial revolution that took place over the last two hundred years are some of the causes. It has affected the Earth's climate system and caused global-scale changes. The Republic of Azerbaijan also contributes its efforts in the fight against the consequences of climate change. Under the priority of "A Clean Environment and Green Growth Country," efforts are being made to improve the environment, restore and expand greenery, and ensure the efficient use of water resources and sustainable energy sources. The declaration of the Karabakh and Eastern Zangezur regions as a "green energy zone" is not coincidental, as it is a response to the ecological damage caused by Armenia's environmental crimes, aiming to restore and promote sustainable energy solutions in these areas. Located in the southwest of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the Zangilan district, which is part of the Eastern Zangezur Economic Region, includes various landscape elements. These include the area's relief, climate, hydrology, soil-vegetation cover and other related components.

The assessment of the condition of the landscape elements in the Zangilan district has been carried out using satellite imagery from the **Landsat-9** and **Sentinel-2B** satellites. For **Landsat-9**, the radiometric resolution has been increased from 12 bits to 14 bits. This capability is especially useful for monitoring environmental changes, such as changes in water quality, forest health, and land cover, in regions that are otherwise challenging to analyze due to low reflectance or dense vegetation. With its higher radiometric resolution "Landsat-9" is capable of distinguishing 16,384 different levels of reflectance within a given wavelength. The "Sentinel-2" satellite is equipped with an optical-electronic multispectral sensor that operates across 13 spectral channels, ranging from the visible and near-infrared spectral bands to the short-wave infrared spectrum. One of the main advantages of Sentinel-2 satellite imagery, compared to images from other satellites, is its high spatial resolution. The Sentinel-2 imagery offers a wide spectral range, with 13 spectral bands covering from visible to short-wave infrared wavelengths. This broad spectrum allows for detailed analysis of various surface features, such as vegetation, water bodies, soil, and urban areas. This, in turn means that vegetation objects can be accurately classified. The NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index) map characterizing the vegetation cover of the area has been created using ArcGIS 10.3 software, based on imagery from the Landsat-9 satellite. Based on the data obtained from Sentinel-2B satellite imagery, other vegetation indices have been calculated, and the description of each vegetation index has been displayed.

Using the program, the area (in hectares) covered by different types of land cover, including water, soil, moderately dense vegetation, and dense vegetation, has been calculated, and the corresponding percentage values have been provided for each land cover type within the study area.

Keywords: Landscape elements, "Landsat-9", Sentinel-2B, satellite image, NDVI

Z-SET BASED INFERENCE USING ALI-1 IMPLICATION FOR CONTROL SYSTEM DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

Fuzzy implication is a cornerstone of various domains, including fuzzy control, multivalued mathematical logic, approximate reasoning, and data analysis. It constitutes the foundation of approximate reasoning and fuzzy logic systems. In many fuzzy rule-based frameworks, the inference process relies on the utilization of fuzzy implications.

A significant challenge within fuzzy implication lies in its representation, which directly influences the outcomes of the inference process. Knowledge-based systems often operate with bimodal information, encompassing both fuzzy and probabilistic characteristics. The scientific literature abounds with studies focusing on fuzzy and probabilistic reasoning, underscoring their broad applicability in both theoretical and practical contexts. It is evident that the choice of implication function significantly impacts the results of reasoning.

In this work, a novel inference methodology is introduced, based on the Ali-1 implication combined with Z-set representations for antecedents and consequents. This approach effectively integrates fuzzy and probabilistic uncertainties, preserving the fundamental properties of information characterized by both probability and fuzziness. The proposed framework is designed to retain the core attributes of information while enhancing the reasoning process in scenarios with imperfect or incomplete data.

This reasoning method incorporates a combination of fuzzy and probabilistic implication operators, distance and similarity measures, and aggregation techniques. Its applicability spans a range of decision-making problems where information is represented using probabilities and membership functions. To demonstrate its practical utility, the proposed methodology has been implemented using the Z-lab toolbox and a table processor.

Keywords: Z-set, bimodal information, Ali-1 fuzzy implication, probabilistic implication, Z-If-Then rules.

AI-BASED NDT DIAGNOSTICS FOR SUSTAINABLE GREEN WORLD

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ABSTRACT

The application of artificial intelligence (AI) to non-destructive testing (NDT) technologies offers a unique opportunity for improvement in sustainability from an environmental and operational perspective. This paper looks into certain sectors where such AI enhanced NDT applications can minimize generation of material waste, enhance energy efficiency and effective predictive maintenance. Thanks to AI techniques, which automate detection of deformities, great quantities of resources no longer need to be consumed as early signs of weakness in materials and structures are detected quickly through scanning. This benefits the equipment since it can be monitored in real time, thereby enhancing the lifespan of equipment and lowering failure rates, further reducing the industrial carbon emission. AI-enabled NDT is particularly beneficial in the building, transportation and renewable energy sectors where the ecological and economic benefits are compatible with the goals of green technology. For example, in building, AI-NDT detects flaws in the structure at an early stage thus limiting repair activities while enhancing building infrastructural sustainability. In transportation, it helps increase the life span of vehicles thereby reducing the frequency of maintenance and emissions. In renewable energy, AI assists in keeping the equipment efficient, preventing energy wastage while lessening the impact on the environment. This study includes simulations and case studies, showing how AI-based NDT can be effectively deployed across these sectors. Finally, the paper discusses potential barriers and the evolving role of AI in NDT, emphasizing its future contributions to sustainability. With its capacity for continuous improvement, AI-aided NDT holds the potential to support a more sustainable industrial landscape, merging efficiency with eco-conscious practices and promoting a green future.

Keywords: artificial intelligence (ai), non-destructive testing (ndt), sustainability, green technology, predictive maintenance, energy efficiency, resource optimization.

LEVERAGING BIG DATA FOR ENHANCING BIOMEDICAL TECHNOLOGY: A PATH TO PERSONALIZED MEDICINE AND IMPROVED HEALTHCARE

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ABSTRACT

The integration of Big Data into biomedical technology has revolutionized healthcare by enabling the development of personalized medicine and advanced diagnostic tools. This paper investigates how the analysis of large datasets can address critical healthcare challenges, enhance patient outcomes, and drive innovation in biomedical research. The ability to process and analyze vast amounts of medical data-ranging from genomics to wearable devices-offers the potential to tailor medical treatments to individual patients based on their genetic, physiological, and behavioral characteristics.

Big Data enables healthcare professionals to identify biomarkers, track disease progression, and optimize treatment plans in real-time. By leveraging data from multiple sources, including medical records, wearable electronics, and social media, healthcare providers can develop predictive models for diagnosing conditions earlier and personalizing therapies to improve patient outcomes. The paper highlights the use of Big Data in areas like pharmacogenomics, where genetic information can guide drug development and treatment strategies, reducing time and costs associated with drug trials.

Moreover, this paper examines how wearable diagnostic devices provide continuous patient monitoring, offering real-time insights into a patient's health. By combining this data with other biomedical information, healthcare systems can offer a more comprehensive, personalized approach to care. The rise of 3D digital medicine, where patient-specific models are used for diagnostic and therapeutic purposes, further demonstrates the transformative potential of Big Data in biomedical technology.

Challenges such as data privacy, ethical concerns, data standardization, and the need for robust data infrastructure are also addressed, acknowledging the complexities of managing and analyzing large datasets in a healthcare setting. Ultimately, the findings underscore that Big Data is a powerful tool for improving healthcare efficiency, reducing costs, and driving the future of personalized medicine, contributing to a more responsive and effective healthcare system.

Keywords: Big Data, Personalized medicine, Biomarker discovery, Wearable diagnostic devices, Pharmacogenomics, 3D digital medicine, Healthcare innovation.

A NEW ERA IN HEALTHCARE TECHNOLOGY. PREDICTING MEDICAL EQUIPMENT FAILURES: ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE APPROACHES

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ABSTRACT

The healthcare sector is experiencing a technological revolution, with advances aimed at improving patient care and operational efficiency led by artificial intelligence (AI). In order to guarantee continuous patient services and reduce expensive downtime, predictive maintenance medical equipment and failure prediction represent one of the most promising (developing) uses of artificial intelligence. This paper explores AI-driven approaches for medical equipment failure prediction, along with real-time device quality control using data analytics and machine learning algorithms.

Healthcare organizations can change from reactive to proactive maintenance strategies by using AI systems. The main reason is to examine extensive quantities of information collected from sensors and past equipment performance records. Both life cycle and reliability of medical devices are increased by these AI-based solutions, moreover they can provide lower maintenance costs and increase equipment availability.

Nowadays AI advance technologies are being used to continuously monitor equipment, enabling the early detection of performance abnormalities, thereby averting failures before they influence patient safety. Equipment uptime has noticeably improved as a result of these innovations; healthcare facilities have reported up to 30% fewer unexpected downtimes. The utilizing of predictive maintenance powered by machine learning algorithms is also extending the operational life cycle of so important devices such as MRI machines, ventilators, and infusion pumps.

Continuous improvement of AI of course does not pass by in the area of quality control. Its role in strengthening quality control, detecting early-stage defects, and decreasing risks in healthcare environments will become very necessary. By providing more effective maintenance techniques and predictive insights, artificial intelligence is influencing a new era in healthcare technology. By offering enhanced maintenance techniques and predictive insights, artificial intelligence is affecting a new era in healthcare technology.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, predictive maintenance, failure prediction, healthcare technology, diagnostics, equipment management.

The Role of Total Quality Management in Advancing Sustainable Practices in the Food Industry

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ABSTRACT

Total Quality Management (TQM) plays a crucial role in advancing sustainable practices within the food industry, an area increasingly scrutinized for its environmental and social impacts. As this sector faces mounting pressure from consumers, regulatory bodies, and stakeholders to improve environmental stewardship and demonstrate social responsibility, TQM offers a structured framework for continuous improvement that can effectively drive sustainability initiatives.

At its core, TQM emphasizes customer satisfaction, employee engagement, and process optimization. By fostering a culture of quality and accountability, organizations can implement eco-friendly practices that reduce waste, enhance resource efficiency, and minimize their overall environmental footprint. This paper delves into the essential principles of TQM, including leadership commitment, a systematic approach to problem-solving, and data-driven decision-making. These principles are instrumental in aligning organizational strategies with sustainability objectives, enabling companies to navigate the complexities of environmental challenges while enhancing operational effectiveness.

Through the examination of various case studies, this paper highlights successful TQM implementations across the food industry that have led to significant reductions in environmental impact, improvements in product quality, and enhancements in corporate reputation. These examples illustrate how TQM not only facilitates compliance with environmental regulations but also promotes innovation and competitiveness in the marketplace.

Ultimately, the findings of this study underscore TQM as an essential framework for fostering sustainable development within the food industry. By integrating TQM principles into their operations, organizations can achieve a harmonious balance between economic viability and the ecological and social imperatives of our time. This alignment is not only beneficial for the environment but also critical for building long-term resilience and trust with consumers and stakeholders alike.

Keywords: Total Quality Management (TQM), sustainable practices, environmental stewardship, process optimization, resource efficiency, food industry, corporate sustainability

THE IMPACT OF INTERNATIONAL STANDARDIZATION ON AZERBAIJAN'S RENEWABLE ENERGY GOALS

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ABSTRACT

The paper conducts a detailed investigation into the impact of international standardization on Azerbaijan's renewable energy sector. Renewable energy is a crucial priority of the modern era, and the steps taken in this field are accelerating Azerbaijan's transition to sustainable energy sources. Azerbaijan's energy strategy is based on innovative approaches and the application of international standards in this area.

International standardization processes serve as a key tool for the successful realization of this transition. Standards, especially the technical regulations applied by organizations such as ISO and IEC, ensure more efficient and safe operation of renewable energy sources, as well as facilitating Azerbaijan's integration into the international market. In particular, ISO 14000 (environmental management system standard) and ISO 50001 (energy management system) standards play a key role in the development of Azerbaijan's renewable energy sources. These standards systematize the environmental activities of enterprises, helping to increase energy efficiency, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, use resources more effectively, and protect the environment. The application of international standards also facilitates attracting investment and technology transfer to the country. In addition, there are IEC (International Electrotechnical Commission) standards. These standards ensure the reliability and safety of energy systems. By providing standards that increase the efficiency of renewable energy sources, the IEC contributes to the modernization of the energy sector. The declaration of 2024 as the "Year of Solidarity for a Green World" once again highlights the importance of implementing strategies aimed at protecting the environment. In this context, increasing international standards and conformity will contribute to making renewable energy projects more sustainable and creating an environmentally friendly environment.

The paper also emphasizes the prospects for international cooperation and technological development in Azerbaijan's energy sector, and puts forward important strategic proposals for future development. These proposals are related to increasing renewable energy potential, wider application of international standards, and support for environmental projects.

Keywords: international standardization, renewable energy, standards, environmental protection, increasing energy potential.

"IMPROVING OPERATIONAL EFFICIENCY BASED ON THE 6 SIGMA METHODOLOGY: REDUCING WASTE THROUGH DMAIC IN ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT"

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ABSTRACT

As environmental sustainability becomes a critical global priority, industries are under increased pressure to optimize their resource usage and reduce waste. The Six Sigma DMAIC (Define, Measure, Analyze, Improve, Control) methodology offers a structured approach to waste reduction that targets inefficiencies at their source, enabling organizations to achieve significant improvements in both environmental performance and operational efficiency. This paper investigates the use of DMAIC in environmental management, examining its potential to minimize waste and promote sustainability across various sectors.

DMAIC's framework, which begins with identifying waste reduction goals (Define), followed by gathering data (Measure), analyzing root causes (Analyze), and implementing solutions (Improve), culminates in maintaining the improvements over time (Control). This research explains about how each phase of DMAIC can be applied to different industries, such as manufacturing and healthcare, where the reduction of material waste, energy consumption, and other environmental impacts are critical.

The findings presented in this paper highlight case studies which can be successful in various objects, including a manufacturing company that can reduce scrap material by 25% through optimized machine settings, and a healthcare organization that can cut energy consumption by 15% by retrofitting lighting and improving HVAC efficiency. These examples showcase DMAIC's ability to not only reduce waste but also improve cost efficiency and productivity, proving that environmental and financial benefits can go hand in hand.

While DMAIC has shown promise in driving waste reduction and sustainability, its successful implementation requires strong leadership and a commitment to ongoing process improvement. This paper concludes by recommending broader adoption of DMAIC methodologies in environmental management. It also encourages further exploration into combining DMAIC with emerging technologies, such as artificial intelligence and the Internet of Things (IoT), to enhance process improvements and sustainability outcomes. As industries increasingly adopt data-driven approaches, DMAIC offers a powerful framework to address complex environmental challenges and drive both short- and long-term sustainability goals.

Keywords: Environmental Sustainability, Waste Reduction, Six Sigma DMAIC, Process Improvement, Operational Efficiency, Resource Optimization

DEVELOPMENT AND RESEARCH OF METHODOLOGICAL AND ALGORITHMIC SUPPORT FOR INTELLIGENT CONTROL SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

The article presents the results software development and testing for motion detection. A study of the possibility of using robust, neuro-fuzzy and adaptive control algorithms in high-accuracy and reliability information systems has shown that when designing such systems, the developed principles can be used and standard information systems structures can be built.

The development of information technology in the 21st century will be associated with the development and creation of intelligent information processing and management systems in various environments and human activities.

Today, computers have far surpassed humans in areas such as computation, word processing, and more recently even inference. However, they still lack flexibility and lag behind humans in many aspects, for example, in pattern recognition, problem solving with incomplete information, learning ability, predicting the results of a proposed action and developing control, taking into account the dynamics of processes in real life time. Currently, there is increasing interest in mobile mechatronic systems, which is associated both with the practical need to use such systems for the purpose of carrying out work in environments inaccessible to humans, and with the need to study the intellectual abilities of technical systems.

Mobile mechatronic systems (mobile robots) beginning used to diagnose faults in extended and high-rise objects, monitor the environment, search for objects in hard-to-reach places, etc. At the same time, mobility itself can be provided in various ways - these are traditional wheeled systems, and walking, rolling, as well as crawling and flying systems. What these systems have in common is multi-level control of their behavior. Typically, this is a three-level management system consisting of strategic, tactical and executive levels.

Control systems are being developed that provide autonomous execution of a limited set of operations and a number of predefined scenarios, however, as a rule, these are essentially deterministic actions, and their implementation is focused on high-performance computing platforms. The development trends of such systems reflect the feasibility of their implementation on embedded platforms that provide the possibility of distributed control and have, along with small overall dimensions, high reliability and low cost, limitations on computing resources.

Keywords: intelligent systems, motion detection, information systems, software development, control systems, adaptive control algorithms.

DETECTION OF PATHOLOGIES IN X-RAY IMAGES OF LUNG TISSUE USING KOHONEN NEURAL NETWORK

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ABSTRACT

Radiology has become one of the main methods of primary diagnostics of diseases. At the moment, radiology has such research methods as fluoroscopy, computed tomography, magnetic resonance imaging, fluorography.

X-ray examination helps to identify both pulmonary diseases and malignant neoplasms. Automated diagnostic systems are widely used in the processing of X-ray images. However, automated diagnostic systems do not include programs for analyzing X-ray images.

Therefore, the development of a system for analyzing X-ray images is relevant. It is proposed to use artificial intelligence methods for processing, analyzing X-ray images and displaying the analysis results in real time. Pneumonia is an inflammatory process that occurs in the lungs in case of infection.

The problem of classifying lung patterns in pneumonia into two classes of objects is considered: images containing signs of pathologies and images without signs of pathologies. Currently, classification problems are often solved using the capabilities of artificial intelligence systems, namely, using artificial neural networks. Usually, the classification problem is solved using clustering.

The use of the Kohonen neural network is of interest in solving the diagnostics of X-ray images. The Kohonen network is a special type of neural network for solving the clustering problem.

This article considers the problem of recognizing pathologies of the pulmonary pattern using the clustering method. When solving the diagnostics of X-ray images, the Kohonen neural network and Kohonen self-organizing maps were used to solve the clustering problem.

Keywords: radiography, automated medical diagnostic systems, artificial intelligence, classification, clustering, Kohonen neural network, Kohonen self-organizing maps.

PERFORMANCE OF A FIRE DETECTION ROBOT USED IN ENVIRONMENTAL MONITORING

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ABSTRACT

The article presents an approach to the operation of fire detection and assessment robots. The approach is based on a type 2 fuzzy logic system that uses measured temperature and light intensity to detect fires with different intensities at different distances. A type 2 fuzzy logic system is known for not requiring a precise mathematical model and for its ability to handle more complex uncertain situations than a type 1 fuzzy logic system. Due to the lack of experience for new devices, the paper discusses the experience of experts and a new approach for constructing type 2 fuzzy logic parameters from detailed data. The performance of both type 1 fuzzy logic system and type 2 fuzzy logic system on the same fire detection scheme is investigated and compared in the paper. To demonstrate the operation and performance of the proposed type 2 fuzzy logic system, simulations were conducted for both the free space and the new layout fire detection robot. These are mainly used in mobile robots and type 2 fuzzy logic applications designed to model uncertainty in navigation, uncertainty in control, and test different controllers. To prevent a fire disaster, it is extremely important to detect fires earlier in their development stage when there is still enough time for the safe evacuation of residents or industrial workers. Early detection also plays an important role in protecting the company from potential property loss. Property loss can be minimized for operation minimized by early detection because immediate action is taken while the fire is still under control. Fire is very useful to man when it is under control, it serves many valuable purposes for us, but when it is out of control, fire can cause huge destruction and result in terrible disaster. According to the different environment in which fire occurs, it can be classified into different types. Of all the different types of fire, structure fires are the situations that cause the most loss of life and property.

Keywords: fire, mobile robots, simulation, type 2, fuzzy logic, expert.

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ABSTRACT

Fiber-optic cables are used in telecommunications, medicine, agricultural engineering, environmental monitoring, industry, etc. It is widely used in the processes going on in the fields.

The theses are devoted to the issues of accurate measurement of pressure and pressure difference in various transmission processes of fiber-optic cables and data transmission to remote points.

Here, the physical bases of pressure and pressure difference transmitters created on the basis of fiber-optic cables, construction principles, organizers, measurement-information systems based on them, including the issues of creating smart monitoring systems are analyzed.

Fiber-optic pressure sensors are based on the principles of transmitting light pulses through optical fibers and measuring pressure changes. This technology converts changes in the properties of light waves caused by pressure changes into an electrical signal. These sensors record and analyze pressure changes with high sensitivity. Its main components consist of a light source, an optical fiber and a detector. Pressure changes are detected by the detector.

Methods such as Bragg grating (FBG) and interferometry are the basis of the working principles of these sensors.

These sensors are integrated into intelligent pressure monitoring systems, allowing continuous monitoring of pressure changes in real time. Application of fiber-optic sensors in machine learning and big data analysis allows to further increase their effectiveness.

Compared to traditional sensors, fiber-optic pressure sensors are distinguished by their advantages such as high sensitivity, resistance to electromagnetic interference and long-term reliability. The application of these sensors in the automatic calibration of various measuring devices, the detection of their malfunctions and the performance of diagnostic functions allows the automation and continuous execution of various processes.

In the modern era of rapid technological development, sensor technologies have also made significant progress. Sensors have become one of the key elements for creating and optimizing smart manufacturing processes in industry. In particular, systems for measuring the pressure and pressure difference, and the consumption of gas and liquid media transmitted through pipelines are of great importance in various industries.

Keywords: Fiber-optic cables, Fiber-optic pressure sensors, differential pressures, intelligent monitoring, automatic calibration, fault detection, diagnostics.

PREDEFINED TIME FORMATION CONTROL OF MULTIAGENT SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

Climate change has severely impacted worldwide and has resulted in natural disasters in the form of floods or earthquakes. In such circumstances, wheeled mobile robots (WMRs) and unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) play a crucial role as their deployment helps in risk-free operation. However, the operation of a single WMR/UAV or so-called agent is not enough to handle larger scale damage and thus it is required to use multiple agents or multiagent systems. This tends to offer additional levels of redundancy, enhanced operational efficiency, and lower costs than a single agent. Owing to these benefits multiagent systems are used during disaster management in applications including in establishing ad-hoc communication networks, monitoring, search and rescue operations, and damage assessment, etc. Moreover, the coordinated multi-robot systems can monitor air and water quality, providing real-time data to address environmental issues. Additionally, multiagents can significantly contribute to the preservation and management of forests by providing advanced monitoring, protection, and restoration capabilities. To execute such applications effectively, the agents must navigate in a certain configuration. Such configuration of these agents is achieved using formation control algorithms. In practical scenarios, the formation tracking control of multiagent systems is a complex task because it involves the handling of issues like time constraints, environmental uncertainties, unavoidable nonlinearities, maintaining the time-varying formations, and path tracking without compromising the agents' stability. This abstract presents a robust decentralized consensus-based formation tracking control strategy for nonlinear multiagent systems. First, a sigmoid functions-based family of sliding manifolds is introduced that ensures the predefined time convergence of trajectories, that start from that manifold. Later, a decentralized predefined time formation tracking controller is derived for a class of nonlinear multiagent systems. The inherent ability of sliding modes to handle matched uncertainties resolves the requirement of robustness. The utilization of the formulated formation tracking control method is shown by incorporating a case-study of multiple omnidirectional WMRs.

Keywords: Formation control; formation tracking; multiagent systems; predefined time control; terminal sliding mode control.

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